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Business, Economics & Management

- ***Accounting & Taxation***
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- ***Marketing***
- ***Strategic Management***
- ***Tourism & Hospitality***

THE ROLE OF TECHNOLOGICAL TRANSFERS IN AZERBAIJAN NATIONAL ECONOMY

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In 2010-2017 Azerbaijan produced goods based on radical innovations in the petrochemical and metallurgical industries, as well as in the production of computers, as well as absolutely new products in the textile and drink industries. For the period 2014-2017 enterprises of the above industries have spent the main costs of technological improvements in industrial production.

In considering the statistical data by author, it was found that for 2012-2016 and 2013-2017 the share of exports of machine-building products in Azerbaijan does not exceed 0.1% in total exports worldwide. But for 2013-2017 in machinery the value of the volume of growth (-18%) increased than in period 2012-2016 (-24%). At the same time the share of imported machinery goods also does not exceed 0.2% of the total imports worldwide. Machines for the processing of milk, wood, seed selection, crushers, presses, etc. (www.trademap.org) are mainly imported into Azerbaijan, whose share ranges from 0.2% to 0.9%.

According to the author's calculations, using statistics from Azerbaijan, the share of exported high-tech products in Azerbaijan's total exports increased from 2.7% in 2012 to 3.5% in 2017, while imports of high-tech goods decreased from 68% in 2012 to 53,2% in 2017, which indicates the interest of the Azerbaijan government in expanding exports of high-tech products, improving and strengthening the technological equipment of domestic enterprises.

In last years, the import of high-tech machine-building products in Azerbaijan has an important function to update the fixed assets of machine-building plants, food and textile factories. Technological characteristics and design of products of these industries are gradually improving, completely new types and nomenclature of these products are being created, using the advanced technological production lines.

Technological transfers after import of high-tech industrial equipment contribute not only to strengthening the national economy of Azerbaijan on the basis of innovation and investment reforms, but also implies the accelerated development of high-tech industry in the country.

Based on the above author comes to the following conclusions:

- both imports and exports of high technology products and components will contribute to innovative changes in the entire economy;
- the state legally supports the import of technological transfers of high-tech equipment and mechanisms through customs duties, also promotes the export of high-tech products through tax privileges' at the production and sales stage, with the help of customs tariffs at the implementation stage;
- The state legally and financially supports its producers and innovators in organizing exhibitions abroad.

THE ESSENTIAL EVALUATION METHOD OF TOURISM RESOURCES

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The problem of evaluation and recreation and applying universal methods and criterias on this evaluation process is researched by many researchers and different evaluation methods were compiled and suggested.

At the time it should be taken consideration that evaluation of natural resources for the tourism purposes is enough complex problems and until now lack of universal, standard methods of evaluation does result in having non-standard and subjective approach and different resulting in process. So this come from the nature of tourism resources.

In evaluation of resources in modern tourism science technological, economical, ecological, medical-biological, quantity and quality methods, in evaluation of natural and cultural-historical monuments UNESCO method, and in evaluation of regionalization according to the specific tourism types and elements of tourism type mathematical methods are used.

We consider that evaluation of resources has to reflect its essence, i.e. has to reflect the characteristic aggregate of ability to create interest (motive or complex of motives) for tourism. New method that we suggested can be taken into account as a method of essential evaluation of resources.

According to our results of researches we have come to conclusion that properties should be taken main as the criterias of evaluation of tourism resources. These properties characterized with parameters such as attraction, natural location, learning or research level, usefulness for tourism excursion, video-ecological features, socio-demographic significance, method of using ability, available potential reserve, recreation feature, usefulness, energy-information features and etc. We suggest learning these indications one-by-one and evaluation of all of these parameters according to 20-point scale and taking total value as average score.

While evaluation, providing objectivity depends on serious approach and level of professionalism of experts that are realizing evaluation. Attracting special experts while evaluation on different parameters can let us to achieve more objective result.

As we accepted all of the indicators of reserve are evaluated according to 20-point scale and its average score is found. Calculation is made with following formula:

$$Q_{1av} = x_{1,1} + x_{1,2} + x_{1,3} + x_{1,4} + \dots + x_{1,n}; (1).$$

Here Q_{1av} is average score that were given to properties of each tourism reserve;

$x_{1,1}, x_{1,2}, x_{1,3}, x_{1,4}, x_{1,n}$ is achieved score of each tourism reserve.

Total value of tourism reserves of region is calculated with this formula:

$$Q_t = (Q_{1av} + Q_{2av} + Q_{3av} + Q_{4av} + \dots + Q_{nav}) / Q_n; (2).$$

Here Q_t - is total value of tourism reserve available in region;

$Q_{1av}, Q_{2av}, Q_{3av}, Q_{4av}, Q_{nav}$ – are average points given to evaluated tourism reserves of region according to their features;

Q_n – is mean value of the count of defined reserves.

Calculated point of reserve according to the each feature ($x_{1,1}, x_{1,2}, x_{1,n}$) lets us to find its average score with using formula (1). Average score of reserves in region is calculated by dividing each average value of reserves by their count with formula (2). Usefulness level of tourism reserves for a purpose of development of region's tourism is defined according to the final total value (Q_t).

We suggest to determine the usefulness level as follow:

1. Quite useful (16-20 points);
2. Useful (11-15 points);
3. Partly useful (6-10 points);
4. Useless (1-5 points).

As a result of this evaluation using level of reserves can be determined from the reserves that actual characterizing the efficiency of reserves. Except this, while reviewing the tourism reserves of region all reserves or other elements defining the using level of it and actively attracted to tourism process can be evaluated.

DEVELOPMENT OF THE ELECTRONIC GOVERNMENT IN UZBEKISTAN

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The electronic government is based on the distributed information-telecommunication infrastructure, i.e. on infrastructure of electronic government developed in scales of the state and which kernel is the system of electronic document circulation, system of automation of the government. Electronic government is a part of administrative reform of the state for transition to digital transformation of economy. In the decree of the President of Republic of Uzbekistan «About Strategy of actions on the further development of Republic of Uzbekistan» it is designated that realization of Strategy of actions will pass in five directions. In particular, within the limits of realization of the first direction «Perfection of the state and public building» system of electronic government perfection, improvement of quality and efficiency of the state services, practical realization of mechanisms of public control, strengthening of a role of institutes of a civil society and mass media is provided. System of electronic government is representation in the Internet of the information on work of the state structures or payment of taxes where there are such interactions: between the state and citizens (G2C, Government-to-Citizen); between the state and business (G2B, Government-to-Business); between various branches of the government (G2G, Government-to-Government); between the state and civil servants (G2E, Government-to-Employees). The United Nations have published on July, 30th, 2016 the next Review of development of the electronic government in the world countries for 2016 (UN E-Government Survey 2016) under the name «Electronic government in support of a sustainable development» (E-Government in Support of Sustainable Development) where the basic indicator of the report is the Index of development of the electronic government - E-Government Development Index, which estimates degree of development of electronic services. In a rating of 2016 of the Republic of Uzbekistan with index E-Government Development Index at level 0.54335 that above an average world index, and it was included into group of the countries with high level of development electronic government. As a result of large-scale measures of Republic of Uzbekistan accepted in the country has considerably improved a position in a rating of the United Nations of 2016 on level of development electronic government, having entered into 40 % of the most advanced countries of the world and having occupied 80 places among the states applying system electronic government. On an index of electronic participation which estimates efficiency of dialogue of the government with the citizens and business, on a sub-index «electronic services», the Republic of Uzbekistan has occupied 47 places in the world, 3 place in the CIS and 1 among the countries of the Central Asia. Thus on an indicator «help services» of the Republic of Uzbekistan has received the maximum 100 % and has doubled an indicator «high-grade electronic services» - from 24 % in 2014 to 52 %, in 2016. According to the complex program of development of National information-communication system of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2013-2020, the Center of development of system electronic government is created.

The Uniform portal of interactive state services (my.gov.uz) which for today has processed over 1010625 electronic references physical and legal bodies functions. System of electronic government of the Republic of Uzbekistan structure includes following

components: a uniform portal of interactive state services for direct contact to addressees of the state services; a portal of the open data (data.gov.uz) - the data and statistics from state structures; directly sites of state structures; complexes of information systems "Taxes", "Customs", "Formation" and others, through which state bodies "communicate" with each other.

The virtual reception of the President and housing and communal services portal is a system part «Electronic government». According to the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoev, from the beginning of 2017 Virtual receptions also are opened at heads of state structures, heads of areas, cities and areas, rectors of high schools, banks, power structures and so on. The municipal services and available housing E-Communal portal, a national database of legislation Lex.uz functions. Only for March, 2017 in the Virtual reception of the President 445015 references from citizens of the Republic of Uzbekistan have arrived. In the United Nations review also the portal e-kommunal.uz also is mentioned. Responsible civil servants are obliged to answer inquiries and to inform the applicant on the accepted decision. Electronic government of the Republic of Uzbekistan promotes deepening of the state transparency and introduction of information-communication technologies in all spheres of life of the state and a society. Delivery of the tax and statistical reporting, registration of customs declarations, registration of subjects of business and company names became the most demanded online services, the system «Electronic visa» is started. Along with it the uniform mechanism of the electronic auctions on the state purchases, electronic system of giving of statements of claim and petitions from businessmen in the economic courts created in the country the centers «one window» for gathering of documents effectively functions at filing of application on reception of the state services. Thus, citizens and subjects of business have got access to the most demanded and popular state services through monitors or smart phones. For the purpose of improvement of the business environment in the Republic of Uzbekistan it is created a complex of information systems "on one of the main segments of system «Electronic government». Uniform portal of interactive state services my.gov.uz the updated version personal «Office of the subject of entrepreneurship» has been started. Experts of the Center of development of system «Electronic government» together with bodies state and an economic board, have executed great volume of works on the further improvement of granting of the state services, is introduced more than 308 types of service allowing citizens and to subjects of business operatively and easily to solve the questions answers on which give more than 2433 bodies state and an economic board. Since 2015 to regulation.gov.uz address there has begun work system of an estimation of influence of certificates of the legislation which give to estimate again accepted regulatory legal acts. In the Center databases physical and legal bodies, and also a kernel of a base platform of system «Electronic government» are generated. The center creates the Uniform register of the state services, forms and forms, registration of the state services in the Uniform register. Introduction and system development «Electronic government» in the Republic of Uzbekistan is erected in a rank national and within the limits of realization of Strategy of actions for 2017-2021, the potential of development of system «Electronic government», capable to provide a transparency of activity of authorities, optimization of granting of services to the population and business, increase of degree of electronic participation of citizens in government processes will amplify. The electronic government is not addition or analogue of the traditional government, and only defines a new way of interaction on the basis of active use of information-communication technologies with a view of increase of efficiency of granting of the state services.

Chemical & Material Science

- *Analytical Chemistry*
- *Biochemistry*
- *Ceramic Engineering*
- *Chemical & Material Sciences (general)*
- *Chemical Kinetics & Catalysis*
- *Combustion & Propulsion*
- *Composite Materials*
- *Corrosion*
- *Crystallography & Structural Chemistry*
- *Dispersion Chemistry*
- *Electrochemistry*
- *Inorganic Chemistry*
- *Materials Engineering*
- *Medicinal Chemistry*
- *Molecular Modeling*
- *Nanotechnology*
- *Oil, Petroleum & Natural Gas*
- *Organic Chemistry*
- *Polymers & Plastics*

PECULIARITIES OF SURFACE TENSION EFFECTS IN THIN FILMS AND DROPS OF PHARMACEUTICAL LIQUIDS ON INCLINES

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Abstract

Behaviour of thin liquid films and drops, including those that are used for pharmaceutical purposes, in static or dynamic states, and under diverse physical and chemical conditions composes a wide range of really interesting as well as complicated problems, which are significant in both theoretical and experimental ways. The explanation of the peculiarities of special patterns' occurrence and fluid behaviour during drainage down an inclined surface or spreading represents an extremely multifaceted problem. A reliable techniques for measuring a contact angle and studying fluid droplets' behaviour in dynamic conditions, while starting flowing down an inclined plane, are related important points.

Theoretical part

Each liquid is characterized by certain value of a coefficient of surface tension σ that is in charge of its chemical compound. Presence of surface active agents within fluid greatly influences the parameter σ . It is also worth mentioning that dynamic processes of mass transfer due to Marangoni effect are observed during the spreading of fluid on a horizontal plane or drainage down an inclined surface. Behaviour of liquid drops on inclines with diverse properties represents an increased scientific interest.

Experimental part

At the time of preparation of this work numerous experiments with typical pharmaceutical liquids, in particular, antiseptic ones, on an inclined surface and a horizontal plane were held, and also some, which let us observe special fingerlike patterns formed during the flowing of thin fluid film down an inclined surface.

Results

On the basis of the experimental data, the coefficient of surface tension of pharmaceutical liquids was calculated using stalagmometry (method of counting drops); the qualitative assessment of fluids' coefficient of surface tension was made based on analysis of contact angles of a droplet in static and dynamic states (changing angle between inclined surface and horizontal plane).

Discussion

Therefore, at this work the basic systematization of the facts in relation to processes, which occur within surfactants including those that are used for pharmaceutical purposes was held. Furthermore, the peculiarities of behaviour of droplets and thin liquid films on variously inclined surfaces were observed. The possibility to use typical laboratory methods for measuring a coefficient of surface tension and their efficiency were managed to check, and the suitability of a method of photo and video fixation and step-by-step scanning of the experiment to study properties of static droplet on a horizontal plane, the process of starting flowing down an inclined plane and the dynamics of liquid patterns' formation was estimated.

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SAFETY OF INFORMATION-COMMUNICATION BANK SYSTEM

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The analysis of frequencies of potential attacks, type Backdoors on telecommunication systems is highest in the list of potential attacks. Backdoors are the programs, allowing getting access to the computing system bypassing system mechanisms of information security. Backdoors provide access to system from the point of view of the infringer, instead of the system administrator and they are not a synonym of "Grecian horse" though in the literature a number of authors are mixed by the given terms. Usually "Grecian horses" are used specially for performance concrete harmful functional. The analysis has shown that "Grecian horses" can contain Backdoor to a component. Backdoors taking root into the telecommunication system, inherent basic function opens access to the necessary information, deforms, deletes or simply abducts the necessary information. Backdoors can be used for performance of individual remote commands, besides they can open access to the command interpreter of system or even to give to the infringer remote access to the window interface of an operating system. More often «Backdoors» take root infringers in the computing system, and after initial penetration into this system, taking into account vulnerability or errors of adjustment or a system configuration deforms or deletes the necessary information.

As the alternative variant of installation is considered installation Backdoors by the manager of the system, misled by the infringer the user. Usually Backdoors are carried out with powers of the user who has established him.

Activation Backdoors can be carried out in the various ways: depending on OS type, inclusion of programs Backdoors in keys of the register of an applications launch, in auto start folders, in the scenario of initialization of OS etc. is possible besides, start Backdoors can be carried out on set time, by means of Windows Task Scheduler, or UNIX cron.

The Software on protection from Backdoors is spent on the basis of antiviruses, for example antispysware in points of start of the basic program. For Backdoors the program net cat, redirecting standard programs of input and output on UDP and TCP ports approaches. Using net cat, the infringer can create a program cover (shell), passively expecting network connection from the outside, or on the contrary actively transfers such program cover on a network, bypassing the gateway screens blocking entering connections of system.

A sign of work such Backdoors are transferred on the networks specific to various covers of operating systems, sequences of symbols.

There is a version net cat, called crypt cat, providing enciphering transferred on a network given by symmetric algorithm of enciphering. As have shown our researches, as measures of protection from programs from Backdoors are applied the perimetrale and personal gateway screens, but, periodic scanning of open ports of a network is necessary, and also detailed viewing of open ports of local hosts of a network is necessary. But, these measures as have shown researches are inefficient. Some Backdoors provide management of remote OS through the mouse and the keyboard.

Updating's of known means VNC concern such, for example. In modern OS such functionality it is possible to consider superfluous, as any functions of OS выполнимы by means of the interface of the command line which use attracts much smaller overhead charge in the network traffic and computing capacity of system. The basic method of counteraction to detection Backdoors is the transport report, which using not TCP or UDP, and ICMP.

Other methods to counteraction of attack Backdoors, activization and performance of commands is use the network packages received by listening of a network (sniffers). As ports

of reports thus are not used, such means are much more difficult for finding out in bank system. Special programs in bank information systems, use sniffers, working in «promiscuous» an ohm a mode which to find out extremely difficultly as network packages can be addressed at all to those hosts where programs Backdoors are installed. Sniffers can be used also in switched networks of bank system by use of technology of damage of an ARP-cache (ARP cachepoisoning).

For protection from Backdoors probably to use the so-called started processes, with corresponding privileges of the super user, use of system of detection of the intrusions (OWLS), distinguishing signatures of commands Backdoors. As have shown researches, in the course of work of bank information-switching system revealing of adapters, especially in a mode promiscuous, by means of commands of an operating system and appendices (ifconfig, ifstatus, iplink, Promiscdetect.exe), removal Backdoors by means of means of type Sentinel is the most effective.

ARCHITECTURAL AND TOWN-PLANNING ENVIRONMENT AS CONSEQUENCE OF SOCIAL- ECONOMIC AND POLITICAL NECESSITIES

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An author investigates the problem of forming of architectural and town-planning environment in the process of social-historical development as removing of economic activity, political system and tendencies of cultural activity, that represent the public necessities of set historical time. The scientific searches of the last years are directed to research of specific problems of forming of town-planning and architecture in Ukraine as part of former Soviet Union, that arose up and were organized under act of the existing in soviet time political mode. Thus, a research aim is finding out of reasons and directions of forming of the Ukrainian town-planning and architecture for times of stay of country in composition the USSR and in the period of its independence. Research methodology contains causal relationship between the politically-economic mode and tendencies of forming of architectural and town-planning surroundings, a comparative analysis between the stages of politically-economic activity and directions in forming of architectural and town-planning environment.

Specific of the system of rule of Soviet Union, built on supremacy of single-party leading force almost analogical to the separate European states in 1920-1940th remained nearly without changes during all existence of the soviet state to its disintegration. Its difference from the European countries of the marked period was exceptionally a state form of ownership onto everything (so-called socialist economic system, that allegedly was a people ownership).

The specific of the existing for soviet times political mode as communist party that undertook a legislative functions and hard control for activity of executive branch of power (as Council of ministers) and mainly puppet legislative branch - Verkhovna Rada of the USSR create conditions under which power had the opportunity to concentrate the main

functions of programming of further directions of development of the state, planning of economic activity with clear determination of its volumes and deadlines, financing from single state treasury all directions of economy. Ideology of the state with the single-party system of rule: 1) clearly reflected in the corresponding system of order of forming of architectural and town-planning space; 2) envisaged the large volumes of building on the basis of only principles defined by authority and directions in planning of cities, them shaping and style formations; enormous human, financial and technical resources were involved for realization of large-scale works according to a enormous volumes of plans; 3) uniform principles of creating an architectural and town-planning environment were determined by the state in accordance with its ideological programs whose goal was to glorify the greatness and power of the Soviet state, and the stay of the people (“working masses” in according of Soviet terminology) in such an environment contributed to the consolidation of public consciousness to the spirit of Soviet being mythologized by the power system; 4) the separation of Ukraine from the USSR and its people’s democratic social and historical development contributed to the abandonment of the principles of the Soviet architectural planning system and the search for new ways of shaping the architectural and urban planning space.

CHURCHES OF HISTORICAL KYIV

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Kyiv is the capital of modern Ukraine. This is an ancient city that has a half thousand years of history. Kyiv experienced different periods.

The city was built, developed and destroyed by wars, natural disasters and at the request of its leaders. Kyiv was the capital of the independent state of Russia in the first period of its development. The city was the center of local territories in the Lithuanian-Polish period. Kyiv was the local center after the conquest of Russia. Kyiv became the capital of an independent Ukraine in the 20th century.

Kyiv played an important role in the development of the territories of Ukraine. It was one of the main cities, was the administrative, cultural center. Kyiv was also a religious center. Princes of Kyivan Rus developed the city according to the principles of Constantinople in Byzantium. Religion and state power in Byzantium were one. Therefore, the administrative center of Kyivan Rus was also a religious center. In the Lithuanian-Polish period, the city was remembered as a sacral center. When Russia won Kyiv, it developed it as a holy place.

Kyiv was a holy city for the local population. Such cities are in other countries. But Kyiv is a special sacred city, it was different from other sacred cities. Temples of different religions were in it. Most were Orthodox churches. Churches in different architectural styles were in the city. Many trees were in the city. The city stood on the hills. Churches with golden domes among the trees in the hills were far visible. The city had many temples and monasteries. It attracted pilgrims. The view of Kyiv was very popular with those who came to its monasteries and churches.

The relevance of research. In the 20th century, a socialist period began in Ukraine. Many churches in Kyiv were destroyed at this time. Ukraine became an independent state at

the end of the 20th century. Again, the opportunity arose to build churches in Kyiv and other cities. Modern architects lack knowledge of religious architecture. Therefore, the study of the churches of historic Kyiv is important for modern architecture.

The object of the research is the churches of Kyiv of different religions until the Soviet period until 1917.

The subject of the research is the architectural features of the churches of Kyiv and interaction with the urban environment.

The purpose of the study is to identify patterns in the formation of the architecture of Kyiv's churches of different religions, and their interaction with the urban space.

The research methodology includes an analysis of the religions of Kyiv and the history of the construction of temples, an analysis of the architecture of temples, the urban environment and the interaction of temples and their environment.

The result of the research involves the identification of factors influencing the formation of religious architecture on the territory of Kyiv, the laws governing the formation of the architecture of temples of different religions, the urban environment and the interaction of temples and their urban environment.

FORMATION OF A SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT SYSTEM OF "GREEN" CITY TRANSPORT

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The development of urban agglomerations is characterized by two peculiarities: firstly, increasing the efficiency of production and, consequently, increasing the volume of its products, impose an additional burden on transport infrastructure, rolling stock, the natural environment and health of the population, on the other hand, forms the basis for the growth of the purchasing capacity of urban residents, an increase in the number of vehicles, and in the mobility of citizens. Balancing these two effects is an urgent task in any city and country. Moreover, it is necessary to take into account the level of loading on the natural environment of cities, since the realization of the main goal - the quality of population life, it is not possible outside of this condition. In turn, finding an optimal solution is limited by many factors, among which, the national paradigm of the national economy development. There are some difficulties - how focused and consistent is the approach to this task, how preconditions for the introduction of innovative methods, tools, mechanisms for their implementation. That is, the systematization of knowledge, the experience of implementing certain actions, the construction of the paradigm of innovation development within the idea of forming a "green" economy and "green" agglomerations of cities.

The State Environmental Policy of Ukraine, approved by the Law of Ukraine dated December 21, 2010, identified three priorities as strategic goals and objectives for the next 10 years in relation to the transport and road sector: the establishment of anti-noise screens, the creation of economic conditions for the development of clean transport infrastructure and increasing the share of public transport in the general infrastructure by 25%, ensuring the ecological safety and reliability of the pipeline transport.

Despite the encouraging attention from the government to introduce the necessary mechanisms aimed at improving the environmental component of the entire transport system, much more effort is needed by:

- creation of preferential conditions for stimulating consumers to apply those technologies and make decisions about their lifestyle that would facilitate the transition from energy-intensive transport systems based on the use of organic energy sources to progressive ones - biofuels, hydrogen and electricity, with a gradual rejection of biofuels;
- improvement of coordination and introduction of qualitatively new schemes of goods and passengers delivery in the transport sector;
- development of government support programs to reduce the cost of advanced technologies;
- increasing financing of innovative development by the state and creating a system of incentives to support Ukrainian researchers;
- introduction of flexible tax policy regarding venture companies, investment resources of individuals, aimed at solving the issues of ensuring environmental safety of the transport sector;
- the gradual construction of a new infrastructure, including energy saving, for technological innovations, assuming and providing the necessary level of training of specialists for its maintenance and technical support;
- introduction of standards and incentives for the use of fuel of the Euro class;
- the formation of culture of using non-motorized modes of transport in cities and suburbs, and others.

THE ROLE OF INTERNATIONAL TRANSPORT CORRIDORS ON THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE ECONOMY OF AN INDIVIDUAL STATE

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The role of certain types of transport in a country is largely due to its geographical features. For example, in island countries (such as Japan), sea transport is a big place in cargo and passenger transportation. In countries with large territories (USA, Canada, Russia) relatively large role of rail transport, and in the countries with small distances and well-developed territory the automobile (Western Europe) transport dominates.

Due to the density of the transport network, the level of development of individual types of transport and their role in passenger and freight transportation between developed and developing countries, there are noticeable differences. A denser transport network in economically developed countries, about 20 km per 100 square meters. km, and in developing countries, this indicator is already falling to 5-10 km per 100 square meters. km The most developed transport system in North America, it is concentrated about 30% of the total length of the tracks of the world.

In developing countries, transport is a lagging economy and, in general, is characterized by the dispersion of transport systems. There are no railways in the 30 countries

of the world (Afghanistan, Nepal, Niger, Central African Republic, etc.). Rail transport prevails in India, Pakistan, Brazil, Argentina; pipeline in the Middle East, the river in Tropical Africa. A characteristic feature of transport in developing countries is its low technical level. Over the past decades, there have been significant changes in the transport world affecting the global transport network and the role of individual modes of transport in passenger and freight transport. Thus, in the structure of the cargo turnover of world transport, the role of such types as marine, pipeline and gas pipelines has increased, and the role of rail transport has decreased.

In the world of passenger traffic the passenger car transport of individual use is the leading position (more than 60% of all passenger traffic). And if we take into account the bus connection, then in general in the world of automobile transport accounted for almost 80% of all passenger traffic.

One of the most important modern trends in the development of world transport and an important factor in the further placement of productive forces in the world economy was the creation of international transport corridors (ITC) in recent years. This was mainly to ensure international economic cooperation between European states. By the beginning of the XXI century. A major work on the formation of ITC in Europe and Asia has been carried out. As a result, the problems of choosing communications of different types of transport for inclusion in the corridors, development of directions for the development of transport infrastructure of international importance on the territory of the country and improvement of state regulation of the process of forming the ITC system in Ukraine have become the most urgent.

ОБСЛУЖИВАНИЯ АВТОМОБИЛЕЙ НА ОСНОВЕ ПРИМЕНЕНИЕ АДДИТИВНЫХ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ

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На сегодняшний день новые технологии прочно укрепились во всех сферах жизни человека. Подобное «слияние» не обошло стороной автомобильную промышленность, а также её развитие. В наше время инновационных технологий, компьютерные мастера охватывают всё больше и больше аспектов во всех сферах жизни. Добрались они и до автомастерских. Традиционный подход к ремонту постепенно остается позади. Современным специалистам приходится совершенствоваться в плане автомобильного ремонта, используя при этом достижения новых технологий. Эти технологии основываются на диагностике, что позволяет быстро отремонтировать автомобиль.

Главной задачей ремонта автомобилей является дальнейшее развитие централизованного ремонта и оборудования как важнейшей предпосылки внедрения прогрессивных технологических процессов, обеспечивающих повышение качества и эффективности ремонта сложной современной техники, в котором сокращается время и качество технического обслуживание. Создаются новые виды технологического оборудования, позволяющие механизировать, а в ряде случаев и автоматизировать

трудоемкие операций по обслуживанию автомобилей. Разрабатываются современные формы управления производством, которые рассчитаны на применение электронно-вычислительных машин с дальнейшим переходом на автоматизированную систему управления.

Эффективность использования транспортных средств может быть повышена за счет сокращения непроизводительных простоев, снижения трудоемкости технического обслуживания автомобилей. Основная задача состоит в применении наиболее передовых по техническому уровню аддитивных технологий.

Дни традиционного ремонта автомобилей еще не полностью миновали, но их время подходит к концу. И хотя для небольших автомастерских для работы над старыми автомобилями всегда найдется место, маловероятно, что крупные авторемонтные мастерские и СТО останутся на плаву. Ремонт автомобилей становится менее трудоемким и более наукоемким по мере того, как компьютерная диагностика охватывает все больше и больше аспектов ремонта. Технику приходится быть все более и более продвинутой, но не в плане автомобильной науки, а в плане автомобильного ремонта при помощи новейших технологий.

Многие СТО используют базу, которая содержит «историю болезни» машин от постоянных клиентов: стоит ввести номер и её идентификационный номер (VIN), как монитор отобразит все предыдущие сбои. Это облегчает установку нового «диагноза, ремонт и, как следствие, экономит время сотрудников и владельца “пациента”».

Помимо таких баз данных, в продвинутых автосервисах постепенно внедряют технологии, таких как AR, 3D – принтер и т.д., то есть дополненной реальности. Существует специальное ПО для планшетов. Запускаешь программу, наводишь камеру планшета на машину – и на дисплее отобразится информация о поломанных узлах плюс инструкция по ремонту.

Подводя итог можно сказать что в применение аддитивных технологий можно сократить время и качество обслуживание автомобилей.

ИССЛЕДОВАНИЕ ВСПОМОГАТЕЛЬНОГО ИСТОЧНИКА ПИТАНИЯ КОНТРОЛЛЕРА ЭЛЕКТРОМОБИЛЯ

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С развитием мировой экономики ухудшение глобальной окружающей среды становится все более серьезным. Однако загрязнение воздуха, вызванное топливными транспортными средствами, является важной причиной, по которой электромобили имеют экономию энергии и защиту окружающей среды по сравнению с традиционными автомобилями. С постепенной популяризацией электромобилей высокая эффективность электроприводов электромобилей становится важной темой исследования.

Электродвигатель электромобиля снабжен электрической энергией, а электродвигатель преобразует электрическую энергию в механическую. Наиболее

широко используемым источником питания является свинцово-кислотная батарея, но с развитием технологии электрических транспортных средств свинцово-кислотные батареи постепенно заменяются другими батареями из-за низкой энергии, низкой скорости зарядки и короткого срока службы.

Источники питания, которые разрабатываются, в основном включают натриево-серные батареи, никель-кадмиевые батареи, литиевые батареи, топливные элементы и т. Д. Применение этих новых источников энергии открывает широкие перспективы для развития электромобилей.

Электропитание электромобиля разделено на основной источник питания и вспомогательный источник питания. Основным источником питания является высоковольтный источник питания, который управляет автомобилем, а вспомогательный источник питания - низковольтный источник питания постоянного тока, предназначенный для различных приборов и систем управления автомобилем. Электрический силовой модуль транспортного средства является гарантией стабильной работы всей системы.

Вспомогательный источник питания является важной частью электромобиля, поэтому дополнительный источник питания должен иметь преимущества небольшого размера, низкий уровень шума, высокую эффективность и высокую надежность. Обычный электрический контроллер транспортного средства использует линейную вспомогательную мощность, представленную начальным напряжением аккумулятора, подаваемую на регулятор напряжения с помощью напряжения, требуемого двигателем трехфазной обмотки, а затем через три-концевой чип регулятора и другие схемы для управления опорного напряжения. Преимущество этого линейного вспомогательного источника питания заключается в том, что выходное напряжение имеет высокую точность и меньше помех для системы, недостатком является то, что эффективность низкая, диапазон допустимого напряжения ограничен, а стоимость высокая.

Блок питания постоянного тока имеет высокую плотность мощности, малый вес, высокую эффективность, широкий диапазон рабочих температур, широкий диапазон входного напряжения, низкие помехи, низкую пульсацию, низкий уровень шума, напряжение изоляции и многие другие преимущества.

Схема представляет собой преобразователь постоянного тока. Эта схема проектирования передает энергию от источника питания к нагрузке в одном направлении и имеет высокую эффективность и присущую стабильность. В условиях заданного входного напряжения. Когда нагрузка должна вывести больше мощности, частота повторения модуля повысится, чтобы удовлетворить потребности автомобильных генераторов, поэтому это вспомогательная конструкция источника питания, которая больше подходит для электромобилей.

С развитием новых энергетических транспортных средств преобразователи постоянного тока стали все более широко использоваться в новых энергетических транспортных средствах. В качестве устройства преобразования мощности преобразователь постоянного тока является ядром технологии коммутации электропитания. На основе зрелой разработки традиционного промышленного источника энергии инженеры могут разрабатывать различные типы и требования преобразователей для удовлетворения потребностей новых энергоносителей.

ДЕТАЛИЗАЦИОННЫЕ СЕЙСМОРАЗВЕДОЧНЫЕ РАБОТЫ ПО МЕТОДИКЕ 3D/3С И ИХ ОСОБЕННОСТИ (НА ПРИМЕРЕ ЮЖНО-РЕЧИЦКОЙ ПЛОЩАДИ ПРИПЯТСКОГО ПРОГИБА, РЕСПУБЛИКА БЕЛАРУСЬ)

КОЗИУЛЁВ ИВАН ИГОРЕВИЧ

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Важной причиной, по которой применяется сложная технология 3D сейсморазведки, является то, что наиболее крупные и простые по строению нефтегазовые месторождения уже выявлены и разведаны, в результате чего, объектами исследований становятся месторождения с более сложными по строению резервуарами, что приводит к риску заложения непродуктивных скважин. Главные преимущества 3D-съёмки в том, что исследуемые площади равномерно и плотно заполняются обработанными данными (детально отбиваются структурные объекты тектоники и литологии), в то время как в 2D-работах промежулки между профилями остаются непроработанными, соответственно, являются менее информативными. Не смотря на дороговизну 3D-съёмки, она может быть экономически выгодной: бурится меньшее число непродуктивных скважин, эксплуатационные скважины располагаются оптимально и, следовательно, месторождение начинает эксплуатироваться раньше.

Сейсмические исследования методом общей глубинной точки (ОГТ) в пределах Припятской впадины, к которой относится Южно-Речицкая площадь, проводятся с 1964 года и, в разные годы, в той или иной степени охватывали район работ.

Однако, ввиду сложной соляно-купольной тектоники и резко изменяющихся физических свойств осадочных и вулканогенных пород этого участка исследования, а также заболоченности местности и расположения большого количества источников искусственных помех (отработанные пустые камеры, населенные пункты, дороги и т.д.), проводившаяся ранее 2D-съёмка не давала более детальную картину структур, где находятся сложные продуктивные пласты. В данных условиях 3D-съёмка имеет значительное преимущество перед 2D, так как обладает существенно большим эффектом подавления помех. Объясняется это тем, что при 3D-работах выполняется обработка волновых полей, представленных совокупностями сейсмотрасс (сейсмограммы общего пункта приёма, общего пункта возбуждения, общей срединной точки). Также осуществляется частотно-волновая многоканальная фильтрация сейсмограмм и волновых полей с вводом и коррекцией статических поправок с целью учёта неоднородностей.

На сегодняшний день среди косвенных методов исследования самое большое приближение к достоверным представлениям о строении даёт анализ изменения толщин отдельных горизонтов и составляющих их слоёв, выполненных с использованием 3D/3С сейсморазведки.

Health & Medical Science

- Addiction
- AIDS & HIV
- Alternative & Traditional Medicine
- Anesthesiology
- Audiology, Speech & Language Pathology
- Bioethics
- Biomedical Technology
- Cardiology
- Child & Adolescent Psychology
- Clinical Laboratory Science
- Communicable Diseases
- Critical Care
- Dentistry
- Dermatology
- Developmental Disabilities
- Diabetes
- Emergency Medicine
- Endocrinology
- Epidemiology
- Gastroenterology & Hepatology
- Genetics & Genomics
- Gerontology & Geriatric Medicine
- Gynecology & Obstetrics
- Health & Medical Sciences (general)
- Heart & Thoracic Surgery
- Hematology
- Hospice & Palliative Care
- Immunology
- Medical Informatics
- Medicinal Chemistry
- Molecular Biology
- Natural Medicines & Medicinal Plants
- Neurology
- Neurosurgery
- Nuclear Medicine, Radiotherapy & Molecular Imaging
- Nursing
- Nutrition Science
- Obesity
- Oncology
- Ophthalmology & Optometry
- Oral & Maxillofacial Surgery
- Orthopedic Medicine & Surgery
- Otolaryngology
- Pain & Pain Management
- Pathology
- Pediatric Medicine
- Pharmacology & Pharmacy
- Physical Education & Sports Medicine
- Physiology
- Plastic & Reconstructive Surgery
- Pregnancy & Childbirth
- Primary Health Care
- Psychiatry
- Psychology
- Public Health
- Pulmonology
- Radiology & Medical Imaging
- Rehabilitation Therapy
- Reproductive Health
- Rheumatology
- Social Psychology
- Surgery
- Toxicology
- Transplantation
- Tropical Medicine & Parasitology
- Urology & Nephrology
- Vascular Medicine
- Veterinary Medicine
- Virology

HYPERURICEMIA AS THE MIOCARDIAL REMODELING FACTOR BY PATIENTS WITH NONVALVULAR ATRIAL FIBRILLATION

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Relevance of the work. Atrial fibrillation (AF) is the one of the most common form of arrhythmias. The main AF causes are myocardial structural and electrophysiological non-homogeneity. Hyperuricemia is the factor of myocardial non-homogeneity formation, which leads to the microentry waves circulation. However, the prognostic role of uric acid (UA) elevated levels as a myocardial remodeling factor is not well understood and needs to be further explored.

The purpose of the work. To investigate the effect of elevated levels of UA on myocardial remodeling by patients with nonvalvular AF.

Patients and the Methods. We analyzed 103 patient's histories from cardiology departments Oleksandrivka Clinical Hospital. Patients had been hospitalized during 2016-2017, due to the first detected AF.

The patients were divided into two groups depending on the level of UA during hospitalization. Hence, the first group (hyperuricemia) included 54 patients (mean age $59,8 \pm 2,72$) with UA level higher than $360 \mu\text{mol/L}$ for women and $\geq 420 \mu\text{mol/L}$ for men. The second group (normourikemia) included 49 patients (mean age $55,3 \pm 2,32$) with normal UA levels. For the analysis of elevated UA levels effects on myocardial remodeling in each group, the parameters of transthoracic echocardiography were assessed: the anterior-posterior diameter of the left atrium (LA), the end-systolic and end-diastolic diameters and volumes (ESD, EDD, ESV, EDV), the indexes (ESI, EDI), the shock volume (SV), the ejection fraction (EF), the posterior and septal wall thickness (PWT and SWT) of left ventricle (LV). The relative wall thickness (RWT) was calculated according to A.Ganau's: $RWT = (PWT + SWT) / EDD$, LV myocardial mass index (LV MMI) separately for both sexes, according to LV hypertrophy criteria for man and women: $LV\ MMI = LV\ mass / BSA$ (body surface area), according to Devereux. Hypertrophy criteria for man was $LV\ MMI \geq 125\text{g/m}^2$ and for women $\geq 110\text{g/m}^2$. The BSA was determined by the Mosteller formula.

Results. Patients with UA elevated level (group I) have larger LA sizes than normal UA level patients (group II) ($4,3 \pm 0,34$ cm vs $3,8 \pm 0,23$ cm, $p < 0,05$). Patients with hyperuricemia (group I), compared to patients with normouricemia (group II) have bigger RWT ($0,44 \pm 0,02$ cm vs $0,36 \pm 0,03$ cm, $p < 0,05$) and higher LV MMI for both sexes: for men $132,8 \pm 6,3$ vs $109,8 \pm 8,4$; $117,7 \pm 4,9$ vs $103,9 \pm 5,1$ for women, $p < 0,05$.

Conclusions. Our results give an opportunity to make the following conclusion: UA elevated levels by patients with nonvalvular AF leads to LA dilatation and LV hypertrophy with subsequent formation of structural and electrophysiological myocardium inhomogeneity. So, hyperuricemia can be considered as predictor of structural and morphological myocardium changes, which can lead to AF formation.

TECHNOLOGIES TO INCREASE THE ASSIMILATION POTENTIAL AND BIOGENICITY OF THE SOIL COVER OF SUMGAYIT CITY

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graduate student Institute of Microbiology of the National Academy of Sciences of Azerbaijan, Baku.

Technologies for increasing the assimilation potential and biogenicity of the soil cover of Sumgayit city.

One of the problems of the soil cover of Sumgayit (Azerbaijan) is the intensive mineralization of organic matter, low humus content (not more than 0.9-1.2%), a high degree of contamination with organic and inorganic substances, as a result of which their biogenicity decreases.

For man-made soils of Sumgayit, it is promising to develop such methods of recultivation that would intensify the activity of the microbiocenosis, and, consequently, their assimilation potential and self-cleaning processes.

The purpose of our research is to identify the possibility of increasing the content of humus in the soil cover of the city of Sumgayit using biologics, including those containing cellulose decomposing microorganisms.

It was revealed that the use of biopreparations - the association of 3 cultures of cellulose-decomposing bacteria, excess activated sludge, a biological product "Fermi-star" stimulated an increase in the number of cellulose-decomposing bacteria (3-10 times) and the accumulation of total carbon and humus in urban soils by 20-55% . This indicates an increase in the activity of microorganisms in the soil and the formation of favorable conditions for their functioning. The use of biological products and the introduction of cellulose-containing materials into the soil, provided that the optimum moisture is maintained, allows for a short period of 6 months to provide a significant increase in the content of humus in the gray-brown soil. Composting wood and plant waste solves two problems: neutralization of a significant part of regional plant waste and obtaining full-value organic fertilizer to increase the potential fertility of the humus-poor soil cover in the city of Sumgayit. The main advantages of using plant residues and other cellulosic waste (sawdust, mowed lawns, etc.) is to increase the content in the soil of organic substances available to plants. As a result, the soil's biogenicity, their assimilation potential in relation to pollution by organic substances, the potential of their stability and self-purification ability grows.

The use of the proposed technologies in the bioremediation of technologically polluted soils in the city of Sumgayit will reduce the environmental burden on the soil cover of urban landscapes, increase the rate of destruction and oxidative capacity. The developed integrated biotechnologies create the technological basis for the formation of a closed biotechnological economy in the region.

OPTIMIZATION OF THE PSYCHOPHYSIOLOGICAL STATE OF INDIVIDUALS AT THE COMPLETION OF PROFESSIONAL ONTOGENESIS

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The intensity of the involution of human intellectual functions depends on various factors: giftedness and education, which oppose aging, inhibit the involutory process, and also on the personality characteristics of a person, his life attitudes, plans and values. The main feature of the age of late maturity can be defined as the achievement of a state of wisdom by a person.

The feeling of fullness of life and happiness arises in a person when he realizes himself, that is, he actively embodies his ideals and values in activity, using his talents and abilities. Most for an adult, self-realization is associated with the profession and social recognition.

We have to admit that the lack of a systemic psychological approach to the phenomenon of professional non-demand, studies on the prolongation of work activities of the late adulthood in post-Soviet countries, as well as data on possible models for overcoming the crisis of professional demand at different stages of personalization of an individual greatly reduce the possibility of determining ways of psychological assistance in order to provide support for this segment of the population.

The scientific and practical significance of this issue is to optimize the professional potential of people of late adulthood, to develop psycho-preventive measures, to preserve the psychological health of the population involved in work.

The purpose of this publication is to present the results of a tested complex of psychological assistance to people of late adulthood, aimed at enhancing cognitive and creative potential with psychophysiological optimization of all systems and functions of the body, based on a neuropsychological approach with elements of psychosomatic techniques (rebirth).

A comprehensive program is shown to people of late adulthood who are interested in psychological support due to the loss or change of work activity, who are in a state of professional stagnation and not in demand.

The program consists of three blocks: psychological education, direct psychological neuro correction and rebirthing (modification of holo tropic breathing) to enhance and accelerate the effect of neuro correction, classes are designed for three and a half months (be sure to do homework with elements of exercise to maintain the effect).

Tasks of the program. Provide an opportunity to program participants:

- to improve psychological health, to overcome the existential crisis, the crisis of professional non-demand;
- activate cognitive and creative potential;
- to optimize all the systems and functions of the body to prevent or eliminate psychosomatosis;
- to contribute to the prevention of involutory processes in the cognitive sphere in order to prolong a full-fledged life;
- to provide psycho prophylactic skills to prevent neuropsychological, psychosomatic disorders and, as a result, increase the innovative potential of optants of late adulthood.

Conclusions. The comprehensive program presented by us on the activation of the psychophysiological state of persons of late adulthood has shown its effectiveness. Repeated psychodiagnostics showed an improvement in psychological health (a positive attitude toward one's self, to the perception of the environment, to the future). That is, an integrated approach determines the successful professional re-adaptation of a person even in the pre-retirement and retirement age, optimizes the creative potential and propensity for innovation in his professional activity. Specially selected exercises have a stimulating effect on the brain structures, on the so-called sensorimotor level, and thereby ensures the psychological and psychological activation of a person.

ORTHOPAEDIC-SURGICAL TREATMENT AND RECOVERY OF CHILDREN WITH FUNNEL DEFORMITY OF THE CHEST AND SCOLIOSIS

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Introduction. Orthopaedic-surgical treatment and recovery of children with grave funnel deformity of the chest and spine is an urgent problem of orthopaedics and involves a number of complicated and difficult tasks.

The aim of the study was evaluation of orthopaedic-surgical treatment and recovery of children with funnel deformity of the chest and scoliosis.

Materials and methods. The orthopaedic-surgical treatment and recovery were performed in 19 patients aged from 5 to 17 with the chest funnel deformity (FDC) and scoliosis. Isolated chest surgical intervention was carried out in 4 patients. In this group, two patients were surgically treated with the Nuss technique, one patient had a combined intervention with the Nuss and Sulamaa-Paltia elements of surgery using two plates. Taking into account the patient age (under 13) and a relatively small spinal curvature arch (under 45°), the spine surgery was postponed, and these patients stay under dynamic orthopaedic observation. After FDC correction with Sulamaa-Paltia technique, one patient declined further spine surgery. In 13 observations, a staged surgical treatment of the chest and spinal deformity was carried out. In 11 cases, the first stage involved surgical intervention on the spine, the second stage – on the chest. In six patients the first stage consisted of the spine surgery by the Pozdnikin technique (discectomy, ventral spondylosyndesis at the deformity peak, cranial-tibial skeletal traction, correction and stabilizing of the spine with the single-bar endocorrector with dorsal spondylosyndesis). Recovery management included kinetotherapy (deep breathing and breath holding exercises, as well as strength training for the back) and chest muscles electrotherapy, drug phonophoresis. One- to a ten-year follow-up study was carried out.

Results. The spinal surgical intervention was performed in 13 patients. Surgical correction of the spinal deformity achieved 30 to 65°(on the average, 55% of the initial value). Following the correcting surgery, the residual size of the deformity was $46,8 \pm 12,4^\circ$, correction of the primary curve attained $39 \pm 8,9^\circ$. Mean loss of the correction in the 6-month postoperative period amounted to $8,2^\circ$, in 1 year - $12,3^\circ$. Good and satisfactory results were achieved in 12 patients, an unsatisfactory result – in 1 patient. The unsatisfactory result involved an over 50% loss of the initial correction and formation of false joints. The greatest loss of the received correction occurred in patients with neurofibromatosis (31,7°). Following the surgical correction of the spine, in 7 months, a fistula developed in the surgery area resulting in removal of the metalwork and a considerable loss of the received correction. Surgical correction of the FDC was accomplished in 17 patients. The initial deformity index in children with the FDC was on the average 0,7 by Guizhitskaya; after the operation it was 0,9-1.0. In all cases, good correction of chest deformity was achieved with no further loss of the correction.

Conclusion. The combination of the spine and chest deformity mutually aggravates and complicates their surgical correction. Orthopaedic-surgical treatment and recovery of children with funnel deformity of the chest and scoliosis it is preferable to do on the first stage, under pubertal age and with a relatively light spinal deformity.

CLINICAL AND NOSOLOGICAL STRUCTURE OF GENERALIZED PERIODONTAL TISSUE DISEASES IN PATIENTS WITH DISORDERS OF EATING BEHAVIOR

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Abstract

Background. Signs of a harmonious person are a well-being and a healthy lifestyle, the most important factor of which is nutrition. Proper nutrition ensures full functioning of the person, and improper - leads to excessive or extremely insignificant weight, deterioration of the health status and the development of various diseases, in particular, generalized diseases of periodontal tissues (GDPT). The multifaceted behavioral, physiological and medical problems of modern science are disorders and disturbance of eating behavior. In modern society, there is a high level of people with overweight or insufficient body weight. Recently, there is a tendency to increase the number of people with overweight or insufficient body weight.

The purpose - to study the structure of generalized diseases of periodontal tissues in patients with disorders of eating behavior.

Materials and methods. We examined 29 patients with eating disorders aged 16-37, including 19 women and 10 men (the main group). The control group was provided by 30 people of similar age and gender distribution without eating disorders and diseases of internal organs and systems that had an adequate and balanced diet.

Standard clinical and radiological methods are used to assess dental status.

Results. It was found that all patients in the main group had generalized diseases of the periodontal tissues. In 79,31±0,8% of patients, chronic catarrhal gingivitis with a sluggish course and a rare exacerbation of the pathological process in soft tissues of periodontal disease was diagnosed. In 20,69±1,5% of patients with disorders of eating behavior, generalized periodontitis of the primary - I degree, chronic course is diagnosed. All patients in the main group had an unsatisfactory level of oral hygiene, which was 3.2-4.5 points for Yu.A.Fedorovoy – Volodkinoy index and 2.0-3.7 points for the simplified Green-Vermillion index.

Conclusions. It is established that generalized diseases of periodontal tissues are diagnosed in all patients with disorders of eating behavior on the background of unsatisfactory state of oral hygiene. Generalized diseases of periodontal tissues in 79,31±0,8% of patients with disorders of eating behavior are represented mainly by the sluggish course of chronic catarrhal gingivitis, and 20,69±1,5% of patients had generalized periodontitis of the primary - I degree, chronic course.

The high frequency and features of the manifestation of generalized periodontal disease in patients with eating disorders require the inclusion of this contingent of patients in a group of high risk, followed by the development of an algorithm for the treatment of generalized periodontal tissue diseases, taking into account the peculiarities of their general status.

RELATIONSHIP OF THE CIRCADIAN MELATONIN PRODUCTION WITH THE DEGREE OF MUCOSAL INJURY OF THE ESOPHAGUS IN GASTROESOPHAGEAL REFLUX DISEASE

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GERD is common among the adult population of developed countries, is an important risk factor for the development of esophageal adenocarcinoma (EA) and its predecessor, Barrett's esophagus. The incidence of EA is growing; to control it is important to study the mechanisms of development and the relationship of biochemical markers with the progression of GERD.

Purpose: to evaluate the features of daily production of melatonin in patients with GERD their relationship with the degree of damage to the esophagus.

Materials and methods: the study included 47 patients of working age with GERD (mean age 46.7 ± 10 years). All patients underwent esophagogastroduodenoscopy with esophageal mucosal biopsy, quantitative determination of

6-sulfatoxymelatonin (6-SMT) in the 24-hours urine (as well as separately for day and night) by the IFA method, night/day index was calculated. Formed the study group 1 (n=33) – patients with NERD, group 2 (n=14) – patients with GERD: erosive esophagitis (Los Angeles classification grade A and B).

Results: in patients with GERD the content of 6-SMT in the daily urine is significantly lower than in patients with NERD: 47.2 (35.3; 63.1) ng/ml and 83.5 (58.6; 131.3) ng/ml, $p=0.045$. Also in patients with GERD compared with patients with NERD significantly lower content of 6-SMT in the daytime portion of the urine: 70.3 (16.0; 93.6) ng/ml and 97.4 (72.8; 162.9) ng/ml, $p=0.039$. In patients of both groups, there is a violation of the daily rhythm of melatonin synthesis with peak shift synthesis to the daytime. As evidenced by a decrease in the night/day index below 70%: 46% (34; 55) in the 1st group and 45% (25; 56) in the 2nd group. The negative correlation was revealed between the degree of damage to the esophagus mucosa and the level of 6-SMT in 24-hours urine ($r=-0.42$, $p=0.011$) and in daytime urine ($r=-0.37$, $p=0.032$).

Conclusions: reduction of daily melatonin levels due to circadian fluctuations in its synthesis is associated with the development of GERD. The increase in melatonin synthesis in the daytime, with a decrease in the night/day index, is more pronounced in patients with NERD, which proves the protective effect of melatonin (prevention of erosive and ulcerative defects of the esophagus mucosa). The change in the circadian production of melatonin is one of the pathogenetic factors in the development of GERD.

EFFECTIVE USE OF REGIONAL BIORESOURCES IN THE TECHNOLOGY OF BIOREMEDIATION OF TECHNOLOGICALLY DISTURBED SOILS

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The total area of oil-contaminated soils in Azerbaijan is over 25 thousand hectares. The biological productivity of these lands has been reduced to a minimum, these lands have a negative impact on the ecology of the environment of adjacent environments, including the capital of the country Baku with its 3 million people.

In this regard, the problem of developing modern technologies for the rehabilitation of oil-polluted soils and the restoration of their original biopotential is extremely important.

The goal of the research is the most complete and effective use of regional bioreources as components of bio-fertilizers in the process of developing biotechnologies for cleaning technologically disturbed soils.

Computations of the volumes of composts necessary for restoring and increasing the fertility of technologically disturbed soils were carried out. The calculations showed that the total need for composts for the restoration of the biological activity of technologically disturbed soils in the region is about 10,000–15,000 thousand tons.

A comprehensive analysis of biological resources in the Absheron industrial region, which can potentially be used to develop biotechnologies to improve the fertility and biological activity of oil-contaminated soils after they have been cleared from the main part of the pollution, has been carried out.

A systematic analysis of the volumes of regional biowaste (activated sludge, whey, plant waste, yeast brewing, etc.) for research on the development of complex biological products in the technological process of compost production to restore the biological activity and fertility of technologically disturbed soils in the region showed that:

- resources of excess activated sludge in the region are about 14,600 tons;
- plant waste resources are about 36,000 tons;
- resources of whey and yeast brew are about 15000 tons;
- resources of tree plantation and lawn grasses are more than 36,000 tons.

For all selected regional bioreources: whey, activated sludge and yeast brew, on the basis of literature data, their component composition (carbon, nitrogen, protein, carbohydrates, etc.) was found. The results of the system analysis showed that all materials analyzed contain biologically active substances: proteins, carbohydrates, various groups of microorganisms, etc., which are effective for complex composting.

Thus, the results of the work showed the presence in the Apsheron industrial region of a number of organic substances, which are waste products of a number of food and industrial production. They can potentially be used as secondary biological resources as components for the manufacture of biocomposites for introducing them into the technologically disturbed soils of the region in order to restore their biological functions, activity and productivity, taking into account the real climatic conditions of the region - the arid semi-desert with limited natural resources. On the other hand, the effective and fullest use of regional bioreources will lay the foundation for a biotechnological closed-cycle economy in the region in accordance with the «green economy» paradigm.

GLOBAL LONGITUDINAL STRAIN AND GLOBAL CIRCUMFERENTIAL STRAIN BY SPECKLE-TRACKING ECHOCARDIOGRAPHY IN ADULT PATIENTS WITH LABILE DIABETES MELLITUS TYPE 1 WITH FREQUENT HYPOGLYCEMIA WITH NORMAL EJECTION FRACTION

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BACKGROUND:

Determination of Left ventricular (LV) ejection fraction (EF) is the routine clinical standard for determining heart function. Global longitudinal strain (GLS) and global circumferential strain (GCS) have emerged as important LV functional measures. The objective of this study was to determine the early characteristics of cardiac remodeling in adult patients with diabetes mellitus type 1 with frequent hypoglycemia, confirmed by the HbA1c and a two-week continuous glucose monitoring (CGM).

Materials and Methods:

We evaluated 15 stable asymptomatic diabetes patients (Group A) with preserved ejection fraction of the left ventricle (EF: 69 ± 1.77) with inadequate glycemic control (HbA1c: 8.1 ± 0.8) and frequent hypoglycemia (low glucose events: 12.5 ± 3.5 ; average hypoglycemia duration: $103.5 \text{ min} \pm 8.5$) among them 43% females; mean age: 41.3 ± 3.5 years; BMI: 19.8 ± 1.1 ; diabetes duration: 35.1 ± 4.2 years). In group B there were 5 stable asymptomatic sex- and age-matched patients (EF: 67 ± 0.97 ; HbA1c: 8.3 ± 0.3 ; low glucose events: 1.1 ± 0.5 ; average hypoglycemia duration: $76.0 \text{ min} \pm 2.5$; 45% females; mean age: 39.44 ± 7.5 years; BMI: 19.5 ± 1.5 ; diabetes duration: 32.6 ± 6.4 years). 5 healthy controls (group C) (44% females; mean age: 41.4 ± 3.4 years; BMI: 23.5 ± 1.5). For all three groups speckle tracking echocardiography (STE) and echocardiography were studied and for patient with diabetes 14-days CGM, biochemistry were performed. LV GLS, GCS, left ventricular dimensions (LVIDd; PWTd; IVSd), Left Ventricular Volumes (EDV, ESV), EF (by biplane Simpson's method), Left Ventricular Mass (by ASE formula), peak mitral annular velocity at septal and lateral levels (Sm and Sl) were prospectively analyzed offline using feature-tracking software.

Results:

Groups A, B were comparable for diabetes duration and glycated hemoglobin level, history of hypertension, and lipid profile. The EF was similar in the three groups, (A: $69 \pm 1.77\%$; B: $67 \pm 0.97\%$; C: $66 \pm 5.1\%$; $P = \text{NS}$). The stroke volume index (SVi) was significantly lower in B vs A (B: $34.2 \pm 4.7 \text{ ml/m}^2$; A: $37.3 \pm 5.1 \text{ ml/m}^2$; $P = 0.033$). GLS was significantly lower in group A respect B and C (C: $20.9 \pm 1.3\%$; B: $-16.3 \pm 2.6\%$; A: -10.5 ± 0.48 ; $P < 0.05$; $P < 0.01$). Patient from group A also showed more significant decreased circumferential basal (C: $23.2 \pm 5.3\%$; B: $-16.1 \pm 1.5\%$; A: -12.9 ± 3.7 ; $P < 0.05$; $P < 0.01$) and apex (C: $22.9 \pm 3.1\%$; B: $-21.4 \pm 2.6\%$; A: -13.9 ± 1.64 ; $P < 0.05$; $P < 0.01$) and especially severe longitudinal deformation of the left atrium (C: $61.2 \pm 2.1\%$; B: $-57.8 \pm 2.6\%$; A: -17.7 ± 3.8 ; $P < 0.05$; $P < 0.01$) strain rate

Conclusions:

The presence of frequent hypoglycemia plays an incremental role in adversely affecting left ventricular function and remodeling. The conventional echocardiographic methods such as the EF is not so sensitive to identify the early LV dysfunction such as STE study.

INFLUENCE OF THE HEAVY METALS SALTS COMPLEX ON THE FUNCTIONAL STATE OF THE PITUITARY-ADRENAL SYSTEM OF SEXUALLY MATURE MALE RATS

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Topicality The role of the pituitary-adrenal system in the regulation of functional disorders of the hormonal homeostasis in various pathological conditions is extremely important. In some regions of Ukraine, increased accumulation in soils and drinking water of heavy metal salts, which adversely affects the health of the population and becomes a risk factor for the development of many diseases. The urgency of the problem induces the search for natural mechanisms of protection against such chemical aggression. In this work the functional state of adenohypophysis and adrenal glands of rats under conditions of influence of salts of heavy metals is studied with the aim of the future correction of the detected changes.

Method The experiment was conducted on 24 rats, females aged 5-6 months (1 control and 1 experimental group). For 30 days animals received drinking water, saturated with a combination of heavy metals salts : zinc ($ZnSO_4 \cdot 7H_2O$) - 5 mg / l, copper ($CuSO_4 \cdot 5H_2O$) - 1 mg / l, iron ($FeSO_4$) - 10 mg / l, manganese ($MnSO_4 \cdot 5H_2O$) - 0.1 mg / l, lead ($Pb(NO_3)_2$) - 0.1 mg / l and chromium ($K_2Cr_2O_7$) - 0.1 mg / l. The rats were withdrawn from the experiment by decapitation under etheric anesthesia according to ethical norms. The concentration cortisol COR (nmol / l) and ACTH (pg / ml) were determined by ELISA and auto-immunohymulometric analysis in serum. Statistical processing using the Student-Fisher test, $p \leq 0.05$.

Result In experimental animals, the level of ACTH is 194.0 ± 5.4 pg / ml, which is 3.7 times higher than in the control animals ($p < 0.001$, $t = 26.1776$). The concentration of COR in the blood plasma of experimental animals is 73.1 ± 1.41 nmol / l, which is 2.4 times less ($p < 0.001$, $t = 60.72149$) in the control animals.

Conclusions Salt of heavy metals causes profound imbalance in the functioning of the pituitary-adrenal system of mature female rats, which is manifested in the tension of the functional activity of the adenohypophysis and in contrast to the hypofunction of the adrenal cortex. These functional alterations can have a negative simulation effect on the development of stress-limiting diseases in the body, including the endocrine system.

ADAPTABILITY AND PECULIARITIES OF MAN'S SEXUALITY WITH A LOW LEVEL OF LIFE SATISFACTION

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In our psychological studies, certain sexual characteristics of adaptability and life satisfaction in adulthood have been established. Male adaptability is more related to their aspirations for dominance and internment (internality), and is characterized by less tension and integration of individual components of the adaptive structure of personality. Women's adaptability is more related to their tendency to take a subordinate position in social interaction and is characterized by greater integration of components adaptive structure of

their personality. The level of overall satisfaction with life in adult men and women can be not statistically different, but is determined by various factors.

Our empirical study showed the following characteristics of male adaptability in terms of their level of satisfaction with life. Men with a low level of satisfaction with life, compared with men who have a high level of life satisfaction, have a lower level of internment (internality) and desire for domination, less developed communicative abilities and feel more difficult with establishing contacts with other people.

Compared to men who have an average and high level of satisfaction with life, men with a low level of life satisfaction have a lower level of neuro-psychological and emotional stability, behavioral regulation, disability and personal adaptive potential in general. That is, our assumption that men with a low level of satisfaction with life are less adaptive than men with an average and high level of satisfaction with life has only partially been confirmed.

Men with low level of satisfaction with life, who have lower adaptive potential of the individual, are less inclined to constructive sexuality, are less sexually implemented, are more inclined to experience different negative emotions (for example, shame, feelings of guilt, fears and anxiety, irritation and insult to other people) , feel less support from close people and lack of internal forces and resources, are less psychologically prosperous, characterized by lower self-acceptance and less ability to manage the environment.

Men with a low level of satisfaction with life are less satisfied with the realization of their sexual life, more often subject to neurotic sexual reactions, aggressive sex. They are less autonomous, less dominant, have lower communicative potential, do not feel support and negatively evaluate their achievements.

CLINICAL CASE OF ACUTE PURULENT-DESTRUCTIVE PULMONARY DISEASE, COMPLICATED BY NECROTIC FACTIETY AGAINST DIABETES MELLITUS

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Along with the category of purulent-inflammatory diseases of soft tissues cured in outpatient practice of primary health care, which are relatively easily diagnosed and in the vast majority of cases, there are certain forms of necrotic diseases, the clinical course of which is characterized by particular severity and is accompanied by high mortality, reaching from 66 to 76 % according to the literature. Among these forms, necrotic fasciitis is considered the most formidable and unpredictable. In this report, we present one of the clinical cases of a severe form of this disease.

Patient A.G., born in 1947, MC.No. 2023/127 was transferred from the regional hospital on November 30, 2008 with the diagnosis: "Acute gangrenous abscess of the lower lobe of the left lung. Condition after transthoracic drainage of lung abscess. Anaerobic phlegmon of the chest wall on the left. Sepsis syndrome Diabetes mellitus type 2 moderate

course in the stage of decompensation ". Under intravenous anesthesia, an operation was performed: opening of cellulitis of the left half of the chest wall. The revision revealed the spread of a purulent necrotic process on a scale up to 25 cm around the drainage with necrosis of the muscles of the chest wall and purulent flow from the scapular region to the lumbar region to the left. Given the serious condition of the patient, it was decided to perform a radical surgery after preoperative preparation. 12/03/2008, a radical necroectomy was performed with the imposition of a thoracoabsssostomy. Catheterization of the aortic arch with long-term intra-arterial catheter therapy. 12/16/2008, the patient had a cardiac arrest. Postmortem diagnosis: "Acute gangrenous abscess of the lower lobe of the left lung. Condition after transthoracic drainage of abscess of the left lung. Anaerobic non-clostridial phlegmon and purulent-necrotic fasciitis of the left half of the chest wall and lower back. Sepsis. Septic shock. Multiple organ failure syndrome: Acute renal-hepatic, cardiovascular and respiratory failure. Diabetes mellitus type 2 severe in the stage of decompensation". In the post-mortem examination, purulent-necrotic destruction of the lower lobe of the left lung, necrotic melting of the left parietal pleura, granular dystrophy of the liver and convoluted tubules of the kidneys were found. Enlarged spleen and dilated ventricles of the heart. Septic spleen and septic endocarditis.

As this case showed, inadequate drainage of lung abscess with drainage ectopia and its untimely determination ended with the development of purulent-necrotic fasciitis of the chest wall and sepsis against diabetes, the progression of which, like multiple organ failure, was fatal.

EJECTION FRACTION AS A DETERMINING FACTOR OF THE COURSE OF ACUTE MYOCARDIAL INFARCTION

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Introduction. Acute heart failure (AHF) is one of the most dangerous clinical syndromes in the world, and 30-55% of patients with acute myocardial infarction (AMI) who have signs of AHF have a preserved left ventricle ejection fraction (EF).

Aim. To investigate the course of AMI depending on EF, isolating clinically important groups of patients, to reveal the correlation between existing symptoms and signs of AMI with the value of EF, to identify prognostically reliable factors of development of the AHF in patients with preserved EF.

Materials and methods. 114 patients with AMI were divided into 2 groups: group I (EF ≥ 45%, n = 64), group II (EF <45%, n = 50). In each group of patients, demographic, anamnestic, clinical data and a number of general clinical and biochemical parameters were recorded. Subsequently, the processing of received data was carried out in by Statistica software for Windows using the Correlation and Regression Analysis package.

Results. Reliable criteria for the division of patients into phenotypic groups were the values of EF (48.2 ± 0.7% in group I and 30.16 ± 0.14% in group II, p <0.001), ischemia and arterial hypertension in anamnesis (42.7% and 33% respectively in groups I and II, p <0.05), SpO2 level (88% and 81% respectively, p <0,05), CRP level (30,2 ± 0,7 mg/L in first and

48.16 ± 0.14 mg/L in the second group) and ALT (66.1 ± 0.2 U/L and 94.21 ± 0.4 U/L in groups I and II respectively). Prognostically unfavorable factors were: a significant decrease in EF (in the group of patients with EF <45%) and the presence of "marker" symptoms in the group with EF ≥45% (hypertension, diabetes mellitus, angina pectoris, increased CRP, blood pressure etc.). Signs of cardiac decompensation in both groups of patients were independent indicators of the severity of the course of the disease.

Conclusion. In our study we revealed the correlation between existing symptoms and signs of AMI with the value of EF (EF<45%) and reliable prognostic factors pointing to the development of the AHF in patients with preserved EF.

PLATELET RICH PLASMA FOR TREATMENT OF THE KNEE MENISCAL LESIONS

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The knee joint injury accounts for up to 50% of all joint damages. The leading frequency in the structure of trauma of the knee is meniscus (55-85% of all cases of knee injury).

The damage of the meniscus leads to violations of the joint biomechanics, which is accompanied by pain, limitation of movements, instability, contributes to the progression of degenerative-dystrophic processes in the cartilage. Prolotherapy or regenerative injection techniques is popular in Europe and North America. This method is one of the most promising in orthopedics and traumatology and deserves thorough study as alternative for the surgery.

Materials and methods. The study is based on the using of proliferative methods in 32 patients who were treated for the meniscal tear grade I-IIb (Stoller), aged 18-64years old. Due to the lack approved classification, unified approach in domestic medicine to the definition of terms, we consider autologous plasma as the term "plateletsrich plasma" (PRP), when platelet concentration exceeds the norm by at least 4 times and is 1 million / µl and more. To receive PRP, we developed a technique that allows us to obtain a solution with a guaranteed concentration of 1 million and more cells per ml of plasma by two-stage centrifugation of the venous blood. The number of procedures and the interval between inputs were determined individually.

We used next orthopedic scores to assess quality of life in our patients: VAS, Lysholm, Oxford. We assessed the results of treatment as excellent, good, poor and negative depend of effectiveness of treatment. In all cases, survey and measurement were conducted before treatment and 2-5 days after the first injection and futher every 2 weeks.

Results. The majority of patients (27cases) noted marked exacerbation of pain on a scale VAS in the first 2-4 days after injection on average 2,2 ±0.3 mm. After 4-5 day after the injection, all patients noted the decreasing of pain. Subsequently, after 1 and 3 months follow-up, there was a sustained reduction of pain up to 74.8% and 83,6% to grade 0-1.

In evaluating the functional ability of the knee joint using the Lysholm, Oxford scale after 3 and 6 months from the first injection, a steady increase in the rates was observed in 31 cases for more

then 43,6%(Oxford). In assessing the functional ability of the knee joint (Lysholm) after the treatment, an increase in average rates from 70 (before treatment) to 92 in one year was detected. Twenty four patients reported increase of sports activity compared to the situation before treatment. In one patient additional surgical treatment was necessary because of persistent knee pain. We noticed no complications in patients after our procedures.

Conclusion: The analysis of results present the perspective of this technique as an alternative of surgical treatment, but at the same time require the development of a differentiated approach to the use of a method and further analysis.

PATHOGENESIS OF SEPSIS AND MULTIPLE ORGAN FAILURE

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Progress in the treatment of critically ill patients has led to a sharp decrease in early mortality associated with sepsis, acute pancreatitis, trauma, etc. However, in most patients with sepsis, neurological, pulmonary, renal, hepatic and gastrointestinal dysfunctions develop, even under conditions where all infectious foci were suppressed and adequate or even excessive oxygen delivery to all tissues of the body was ensured.

Based on our research, it has been established that the pathogenesis of sepsis is important not only for the pathogen, but also for the response of the body's immune system caused by a bacterial toxin or inflammation products (necrosis), which in its development goes from over-activation to immunodeficiency. The main factor initiating the systemic inflammatory response syndrome is endotoxin, which is a lipopolysaccharide substance, the toxic effect of which is due to its lipid A. The release of endotoxin is observed during the period of death of the microbial cell, including under the influence of antibacterial therapy. What matters is the "aggressive" antibiotic therapy, which leads to the avalanche-like entry of endotoxin from the destroyed microbes into the bloodstream, and the use of subtherapeutic doses of antibiotics used for prophylactic purposes.

Under the influence of endotoxins, the integrity of the erythrocyte membrane, eosinophils, neutrophils, macrophages of polymorphonuclear leukocytes is disturbed, resulting in the release into the bloodstream of a number of biologically active substances - cytokines, such as TNF- α and TNF- β , interleukins (1-6), and others. TNF - tumor necrosis factor - the initiator of the release of phospholipases. Impaired production of NO, inhibition of angiotensin II, which leads to damage to the systolic and diastolic functions of the left ventricle, inhibition of myocardial contractility and arterial hypertension.

Thus, the severity of microcirculation disorders and the formation of multiple organ failure in sepsis and the systemic inflammatory response syndrome depends on the combined damage caused by cytokines of the hemostasis system and immunity.

CHANGES IN THE BIOLOGICAL RHYTHM OF PROLACTIN PRODUCTION IN CASES WITH THE EFFACED FORMS OF HYPERANDROGENIA

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The stimulating role of prolactin in the adrenal cortex and the production of androgens in the adrenal and ovaries glands has been established.

The aim of this work is to determine changes of prolactin production in cases with the effaced forms of hyperandrogenia in different menstrual cycle; establishing of the influence of daily rhythm of PRL to the genesis of androgen's production. Examination of 96 women with the effaced forms of hyperandrogenia was done: basal levels of PRL, LH, FSH, cortisol and testosterone, and a dynamic study of PRL at 8-00 and 2 hours after falling asleep, the excretion of 17-KS and DEA.

The patients were divided into 3 groups: 1gr.- with HRL, 2 gr. - with normoprolactinemia and adrenal dysfunction, 3 gr. with normoprolactinemia. The study of the daily rhythm of PRL in various groups showed a lack of reliable fluctuations during the day in patients with hyperprolactinemia, along with high rates of both the basal level of PRL and 1-2 hours after falling asleep. Chose pathologic forms, there was determined changes of daily prolactin production and its influence to the genesis of androgen's production in different menstrual cycle. More pronounced changes RLP rhythmic products marked in patients with amenorrhea at both normal and elevated at its basal level that was manifested by a significant decrease in PRL after falling sleep ($P < 0.001$. In the second and third groups, there was a significant increase in PRL after falling asleep ($P < 0.001$ and $P < 0.05$, respectively), but its changes were different depending on the nature of the menstrual cycle. However, in patients of the 2nd group with amenorrhea, even at the nominal level of PRL, it was absent increase after falling asleep. For patients of the 3rd group, even with the preserved menstrual cycle and its change according to the type of the extended cycle, a violation of PRL secretion was detected during the day. They were characterized by the absence of its significant increase in 1-2 hours after falling asleep. A parallel study of PRL secretion during the day with daily fluctuations of testosterone revealed the synchronization of the rhythm of their changes even taking into account changes in the menstrual cycle, which suggests that PRL has not only stimulating effects on the production of androgens, but also on their rhythmic production.

Summary: Disturbance of the secretion and circadian rhythm of PRL, changes in the gonadotropic function of the pituitary, disturbance of the circadian rhythm of testosterone indicate the central genesis of impairments in patients with a worn form of HA. The production of androgens in the ovaries and adrenal glands is influenced not only by the basal level of PRL, but also by the violation of its daily secretion

Key words: hormonal diagnostics, women, hyperandrogenia, prolactin

EXPERIMENTAL SUBSTANTIATION THE METHODS OF REHABILITATION FUNCTION OF THE PULP ON STAGES OF TREATMENT WITH ONE-PIECE-CAST NON-REMOVABLE DESIGN OF DENTURES

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The restoration of the functional activity of the pulp of the tooth is important to prevent inflammatory processes in the pulp of teeth, which are used under support of the one-piece-cast non-removable design of dentures and for increase the period of using them.

We have conducted an experiment on laboratory animals. Its teeth were covered with domestic light-curing adhesive with the addition of specialized complex antihomotoxic medication «Traumel-S». After that at 5 individuals who had teeth treated by the above method the teeth were removed 1 week after coating, the other 5 in 2 weeks and the last 5 animals in 1 month. Then they were subjected to decalcification by the conventional method, made of microscopic environments that studied under an electron microscope.

A distinct positive result was detected after 1 month. Macroscopically the edge of the prepared tooth even. Microscopic examination revealed a narrow zone of sclerosis, which are not defined the tubules of dentin. Adjacent to this area tubules of dentin have uneven gaps and blurred contours. On other area the openings are uniform, the tubes are arranged in parallel rows. Odontoblast form a continuous layer, in a surface part of that identifies singular cells with pyknotic nucleus. On other area of the layers to located are odontoplasty of prismatic and elongated form with a wide limbus of cytoplasm and rounded hypochromic nucleus.

Thus, the conducted research on studying of influence on the structural organization the preparation of tooth and subsequent processing of the domestic light-curing adhesive material in combination with specialized complex antihomotoxic medication, showed that the use of these drugs helps to reduce the symptoms of the inflammatory process in the pulp. Compared to the previous series revealed that the inflammatory process in the early stages of observation has ill-defined character and to disappear to 14 day after preparation of the teeth. Changes in dentine in the early period of observation (7 days), not progressing in the later stages of the study (30 days). Changes in the layer odontoblasts are adaptive-compensatory in character, which does not lead to the violation of predentine and strengthening the destructive irregularities in the dentin. The obtained data prove the possibility of recovery of the receptor apparatus of intact teeth after operation of preparation of hard tissues.

CREATION OF DOMESTIC HIGH-EFFICIENCY IMMUNOMODULATING PREPARATIONS FOR THERAPY AND PREVENTION OF ONCOLOGICAL DISEASES OF HUMAN

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Increasing the effectiveness of treatment of patients with malignant neoplasms is one of the most urgent problems of modern oncology. The main methods of therapy of oncopathology (surgical intervention, chemo- and radiotherapy) are aimed only at eliminating the tumor, but can not remove all tumor cells from the body. The most optimal in oncological practice is the use of immunomodulators (MI), which in therapeutic doses restore the functions of the immune system. The modern methods of biotherapy used in oncology include: active immunotherapy with the use of cellular (autologous and allogenic) and non-cellular (gangliosides, heat shock proteins, DNA, recombinant peptides) vaccines. In recent years, drugs of microbial origin are of particular interest among immunomodulating agents. The purpose of our research was to study the effect of Avidin and Lactopropolis on the inhibition of tumor formation in BALB / c mice with transplanted tumor cells of adenocarcinoma of the large intestine (ACATOL). Thus, the new Avidin preparation, when administered to experimental mice intraperitoneally 3 days prior to the transplantation of tumor cells of adenocarcinoma of the large intestine, the percentage of tumor inhibition (% TPO) was 43.18% by mass, -58.0% by volume; For 6 days, respectively, by weight 63.6% and 76.5%. The drug, consisting of dead cells *Propionibacterium avidum1*, had a high anticarcinogenic activity, which indicates the promise of using this drug as a bacterial vaccine. The preparation "Lactopropolis", consisting of probiotic live cultures *L.casei* 925ak, *P. avidum1* and propolis (1% and 5%) with a re-oral administration in the form of a suspension 3 times a day 10 days before inoculation of the tumor of the transplanted adenocarcinoma of the large intestine showed a high degree of anticarcinogenic action (% of SRW was up to 84%). In both cases, stimulation of the immune system was established, in particular activation of macrophages, an increase in the expression of CD 16 receptors of natural killer cells in 1,6-1,7 times. We have checked the data on acute toxicity showed harmlessness and lack of active toxicity. The need for the use of immunomodulators in oncology is associated not only with pathogenetic features of diseases, but also with the methods of their treatment: chemo- and radiotherapy, as well as any surgical interventions induce or aggravate secondary immune deficiency. Nevertheless, drugs of this class can be extremely useful for reducing the side effects of traditional antitumor therapy and for the prevention and treatment of concomitant infectious complications.

СРАВНЕНИЕ ЧАСТОТЫ ВСТРЕЧАЕМОСТИ ОДНОНУКЛЕОТИДНОГО ВАРИАНТА СУРЗА5*3 В УЗБЕКСКОЙ ПОПУЛЯЦИИ

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На сегодняшний день большое значение в практической медицине отводится фармакогенетическим исследованиям. Известно, что большую роль в эффективности и

безопасности применения лекарственных средств играют фармакокинетика, фармакодинамика и метаболизм используемых препаратов. Одну из главных ролей в метаболизме лекарственных веществ играют ферменты цитохрома P450. Эти ферменты метаболизируют большую часть ксенобиотиков. Так например известно, что ген CYP3A5 участвует в метаболизме иммуносупрессивных препаратов, ингибиторов кациневрина, широко применяемых в нефрологии и трансплантологии. Однако имеются противоречивые данные о эффективности и безопасности иммуносупрессивных препаратов. Это явление может быть вызвано присутствием в популяции различных вариантов последовательности нуклеотидов в гене цитохрома. Так, известно, что у носителей однонуклеотидного варианта CYP3A5*3 (A6986G, rs776746) скорость работы цитохрома снижена, что ведет к повышению концентрации уровня такролимуса. Известно, что у пациентов с генотипом GG могут более выражено проявиться эффекты гепатотоксичности такролимуса. Важным моментом является наличие популяционных особенностей в распределении частоты встречаемости данного полиморфизма. По данным многих исследований частота встречаемости CYP3A5*3 имеет свои географические особенности, так например, частота распределения аллелей напрямую зависит от удалённости региона от экватора. Так, в африканской популяции данный полиморфизм встречается наиболее редко (0,06 в Нигерии), а в европейской (0,96 во Франции) и восточноазиатской популяциях (0,95 в Китае) наиболее часто. В связи с этим представляет большой интерес изучение частоты данного полиморфизма в узбекской популяции.

Целью данного исследования было изучить частоту встречаемости однонуклеотидного варианта CYP3A5*3 (A6986G, rs776746) в узбекской популяции.

Материалы и методы

Исследование выполнено в Институте Иммунологии и геномики человека АН РУз. Всего нами было обследовано 51 человек, узбекской национальности. При отборе лиц для настоящего исследования учитывалась их национальная принадлежность в трех поколениях. В группе больных было 28 женщин и 23 мужчин, средний возраст составил $45,41 \pm 9,51$. Материалом для выделения ДНК служила венозная кровь из локтевой вены объемом 3-5 мл (для забора крови использовались вакуотайнеры Beckton-Dickinson) с антикоагулянтом/консервантом 15% трикалийевым EDTA (Ethilendianin-tetraacetic acid). Для получения геномной ДНК использовали двухэтапный метод лизиса клеток крови. Очистка лизатов лейкоцитарной массы основана на методе спиртово-солевой обработки по S. Miller и соавт. (1988) в модификации, предложенной лабораторией Стенфордского Университета. Типирование полиморфизма CYP3A5 G6986A проводили при помощи наборов «Лекарственное средство-такролимус, CYP3A5 G6986A» («Геноотехнология-Литех», Москва) с использованием метода PCR. Для оценки полученных результатов и проведения статистической обработки данных в данной работе использовался пакет программ Arlequin 2015 (версия 3.5.2.2), Excel 2007, SISA.

Результаты

По данным исследования 51 здоровый доброволец узбекской национальности.

Генотип AA по CYP3A5*3 обнаружен не был, AG встречался у 9,8 % (n = 5), GG у 90,2 % (n = 46) обследованных, частота встречаемости A аллели составила 0,049, частота G аллели 0,95. χ^2 по Харди-Вайнбергу составил 0,09804 p = 1,0.

Таким образом, в данном исследовании была определена частота встречаемости однонуклеотидного варианта CYP3A5*3 (A6986G, rs776746) в группе практически здоровых лиц узбекской популяции. Полученные результаты могут помочь при проведении дальнейших фармакогенетических исследований, полученные данные могут быть использованы в качестве контрольной группы.

ОПИСАНИЕ КЛИНИЧЕСКОГО СЛУЧАЯ СИНДРОМА ПРИОБРЕТЕННОГО УДЛИНЕНИЯ QT-ИНТЕРВАЛА, КАК ПРЕДИКТОРА ВНЕЗАПНОЙ СМЕРТИ, ВСЛЕДСТВИЕ ПРИМЕНЕНИЯ ФИТОПРЕПАРАТОВ

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экспертизы.

В данном сообщении предоставляется клинический случай СУИQT у пациентки А.У, 1962 года рождения, диагностированный после приема смеси трав из: пижмы, коры дуба и полыни внутрь, в течение 9 месяцев. Пациентка поступает в приемного отделения ГБ№2 г.Астана по СМП с жалобами: на внезапно возникающую одышку, ноющие, давяще - колющие боли в области сердца, иррадиирующие в левую руку, онемение левой руки, тошноту и потерю сознания. Из анамнеза заболевания выясняется, вышеуказанные жалобы беспокоят в течении недели, первая потеря сознания в общественном транспорте неделю назад. В тот момент по линии СМП была доставлена в приемном отделение ГБ№2 г.Астана, на предмет исключения неврологической очаговой симптоматики. Была осмотрена неврологом, исключена очаговая симптоматика, отпущена на дообследование в амбулаторных условиях с диагнозом: «Синкопе неясного генеза». При повторном ухудшении родственниками вызвана бригада СМП. Доставлена в ГБ №2 г.Астана с диагнозом: ОКСБПСТ. В приемном отделении зафиксирована АД 90/60 мм.рт.ст, снята ЭКГ, в котором: Ритм синусовый, прерывается с единичными ЖЭС, ЧСС 60 уд в мин. Депрессия сегмента ST на 1-1,5мм в I,II,III, AVF,V3-V6. Интервал QTc – 470мсек. Взят анализ на тропонин I -0,01нг/мл, результат отрицательный. По данным ЭХОКГ: Аортосклероз. Уплотнение створок АК. ДДПЖ. Гипертрофии стенок ЛЖ нет. МР 2ст. ТР 1ст. РСДЛА-32мм.рт.ст. Легочная гипертензия 1ст. Полости сердца не расширены. Зон нарушения локальной сократимости ЛЖ не выявлено. Систолическая функция ЛЖ удовлетворительная. ФВ-58%. Выпота в полости перикарда не выявлено. Учитывая жалобы, анамнез, ЭКГ данные пациентка госпитализирована с предварительным диагнозом: ОКСБПСТ, очень высокий риск. Шкала Грэйс 168 баллов. (Критерии риска – синкопе расцененное как, на фоне жизнеугрожающей аритмии), направлена в АГЛ для экстренной КАГ, в котором нарушении проходимости сосудов сердца не выявлено.

Пациентка после КАГ переведение в отделение кардиологии для дальнейшего обследования. За время наблюдения по данным ЭКГ у пациентки было выявлено прогрессирующее удлинение интервала QT. По данным суточного мониторирования ЭКГ: Основной ритм синусовый. Средняя ЧСС 64 в мин, мин 44 в мин, макс 116 в мин. Пауз более 2,0 сек не выявлено. Удлинение интервала QT днем 540мсек, ночью 540 мсек. За период мониторирования ЭКГ зарегистрировано 5825 полиморфных ЖЭС, из них 12 парных, 122 эпизода желудочковой бигемии, 23 тригемии, 38 пробежек ЖТ из 3,4,5,6,7,9 комплексов, макс ЧСС в эпизоде 247 в мин. СВЭ 4433. В ходе опроса у пациентки было выявлено применение отвара фитопрепаратов в виде пижмы, коры дуба и полыни внутрь 2 раза в день в течение 9 месяцев, по поводу, когда то диагностированной недостаточности митрального клапана 1 степени по совету травницы. После отмены отвара трав из: пижмы, коры дуба и полыни у пациентки наблюдалась положительная динамика в виде укорочения удлиненного интервала QT по данным ЭКГ и суточного мониторирования ЭКГ через 4 дня: Интервал QT днем равен 385-420 мсек, ночью 408-420 мсек. Уменьшение ЖЭС, СВЭ.

Таким образом, после отмени смеси трав из : пижмы, коры дуба и полыни у пациентки зафиксировано положительная динамика в виде укорочения удлиненного интервала QT по данным ЭКГ, улучшение состояния в виде исчезновения приступов потери сознания.

Humanities, Literature & Arts

- *African Studies & History*
- *American Literature & Studies*
- *Asian Studies & History*
- *Canadian Studies & History*
- *Chinese Studies & History*
- *Communication*
- *Drama & Theater Arts*
- *English Language & Literature*
- *Epistemology & Scientific History*
- *Ethnic & Cultural Studies*
- *Feminism & Women's Studies*
- *Film*
- *Foreign Language Learning*
- *French Studies*
- *Gender Studies*
- *History*
- *Humanities, Literature & Arts (general)*
- *Language & Linguistics*
- *Latin American Studies*
- *Literature & Writing*
- *Middle Eastern & Islamic Studies*
- *Music & Musicology*
- *Philosophy*
- *Religion*
- *Sex & Sexuality*
- *Visual Arts*

CREATION OF THE SPACE DIMENSIONS IN THE COMPOSITION OF THE GROUP PORTRAIT: A PAINTING OF JOHN SINGER SARGENT «DAUGHTERS OF EDWARD DARLEY BOIT»

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A unique approach to the composition of the painting *The Daughters of Edward Darley Boit* (1882) by Sargent provoked a critical attitude of artist's contemporaries. The painting is half a portrait and half an interior scene as figures of the girls are obscured. This attribute is antithetical to conventional portraiture and one that, combined with the lack of connection between the girls, stymied critics when the painting was first displayed. The analysis of the role of space dimension in the portrait will help to understand the new trends in the painting of the period under study. Its unusual format was inspired by the art of both the past and the present, a characteristic approach that Sargent employed to make paintings that seemed simultaneously traditional and modern.

Spatial dimension is the most important visual component of the composition of the group portrait. The unique way in which the artist employed this tool helps to uncover the idea of the art piece. The light and liner perspective are the main artistic devices that help to construct space in the picture. The interior is of particular importance, including rooms with opened doors, a mirror with a reflection of the window, furniture, decorative vases, and a carpet. The use of these elements is common to the "backstage" composition of a group portrait. Using the "backstage" composition, Sargent placed the Boit girls in an indeterminate space — the entrance hall, neither entirely public nor entirely private — that is brightly lit in the foreground but recedes into a vaguely defined drawing room half-lit with mirrors and reflections. The wall and the large Japanese vase standing next to it play the role of a "backstage" in the left part of the canvas. In the right part of the painting, "backstage" is represented by a fragmentary depicted vase (a twin of the first one) and an oriental folding screen. The scene creates a border of light and shade, divides the space into a lighted hall and apartments that are immersed in shadows.

The division of space into several dimensions distracts the viewer's gaze from the illuminated part of the foreground to depth. The effect of a perspective reduction is emphasized by the diagonals of the carpet (and its ornament), the parquet floor, the mantelpiece, and the change of the scale of the vases. The reflection of the window in the mirror expands the space in the picture. The artist plays with the scale of the figures; the figures in the lighted part of the canvas are contrasted in space and saturated in tone, the silhouettes of older girls, recede progressively into the shadows, becoming increasingly indistinct. Asymmetry, as the principle of construction of the art piece under consideration, enhances the perception of dynamics. The natural poses of girls, the mobility and variability of space correspond to the mood of a child's portrait.

The asymmetry is the basis for the construction of the "backstage composition" of the painting. Diagonal lines, different scales of the objects, and the reflection in the mirror are enhanced by the forms cut in the perspective. The depth of space of the group portrait is created by the contrasting collision of light and shadow, which divides the canvas into several dimensions.

Sargent demonstrates his mastery based on the study of artistic heritage. The historical precedent for the Boit portrait can be found in the work of Spanish master Diego Velázquez, an artist greatly admired by Sargent. Sargent adapted Velázquez's mysterious space, his dark subdued palette. At the same time, Sargent followed the contemporary trends. It is possible to notice the similarities between Sargent's painting and the portrait of Edgar Degas *The Bellelli Family* (1862), which anticipated the direction of impressionism. The painting *Daughters of*

Edward Darley Boit shares some of Degas's strategies: the asymmetrical composition with an almost empty center, the sense of disconnection between family members, and a feeling of modern life interrupted. Sargent abandons the traditional iconography of the custom group portrait, which is dominated by the image of a person. The psychological expressiveness of the group portrait of The Daughters of Edward Darley Boit is based primarily on the expression of a spatial, tonal, minimalist coloristic solution. Space dimension plays a leading role in the portrait characterization of models, which can be defined as a trend in the art of the late XIX – early XX century.

SOUND MAKING AS A BRANCH OF ART IN UKRAINE

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Nowadays it is safe to assert that sound-making is an integral part in the modern world, as well as the necessary component of a modern cultural space, possessing specific means of artistic expression that are constantly modified and enriched, objectively reflecting changes and innovations in artistic technologies.

Analyzing the practical experience that has been accumulated over one hundred years of historical development of sound recording, some regularities have been identified which imply the creative specificity of this type of musical work. The existence of other approaches in creating a virtual sound space proves the uniqueness of sounding phonograms. In addition, the existence of a unique sound-making style is empirically proven, although scientific reflection is absent.

Until now, the issues of creative and artistic nature and the place of the sound engineer in the artistic chain remain unresolved: the author - the performer - the listener; the unsolved problem of scientists-researchers remains the history of sound-making in Ukraine and the creative work of Ukrainian sound engineers; the notion of a sound composition as a unique structure that can change during the creative work of the sound engineer is not established; require significant improvement in the methods of interpreting the sound image of a musical composition in the recording.

The present changes in evolution of technology, as well as realities in Ukraine and abroad, need innovation in the media.

In the context of our study, we will pay special attention to the clarification of the essence and content of the notion of sound-making and its differences from related concepts. Among the various definitions of content, one can distinguish such as "music producer", "master", "sound engineer" and "sound producer".

It should be noted that taking into account the possibility of fixing audio information in digital form, without loss of quality, the sound worker takes his niche in preserving the cultural heritage of our time. Depending on the original material provided, the degree of deviation from the original design, the interpretation may vary: from a minor (amplitude-frequency and dynamic) technical correction to a significant creative processing. The combination of selected methods of recording and means of artistic expression directly affect the aesthetics and artistic quality of the phonogram.

After analyzing the main specialists' approaches according to the definition of this concept, we can propose our own definition. Thus, in our opinion, the sound engineer is a specialist in the field of audio industry, who implements the creative idea of the author through the technical transformation and processing of audio, using modern technology.

Thus, using the set of methods the tasks have been achieved, namely: the degree of study of the issue of sound engineering in Ukraine has been studied, the evolution of sound technologies

has been considered and the modern sound standards have been analyzed in order to introduce the sound design into the national sound work activities.

ACTIVITIES OF THE MAIN EDUCATIONAL AND OUTREACH HUBS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF JAZZ CULTURE WITHIN THE UKRAINIAN SOCIETY

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Starting with the mid-20th century, after absorbing the entire global experience and despite the complicated adaptation and dissemination methods, jazz art managed to gain a foothold in the Ukrainian culture, successfully develop, and move to a new global level. This was actively facilitated by numerous jazz events, festivals, contests, etc. They were preceded by considerable organizational work done by various hubs, which presupposed the activities of an entire network of state, public, and private structures. No significant results could be achieved without their concerted efforts. A great amount of work was done on forming jazz traditions in Ukraine, the establishment of a powerful media space and the atmosphere of a positive perception of jazz art by the general audience. Its **topicality** is determined by the research of certain entity activities with account for their significant share in the popularization of jazz culture in Ukraine.

It is clear from the scientific research that outline of the complex of educational and outreach jazz hubs and determining their role in spreading the Ukrainian jazz culture did not become the subject of the research for national researchers. And hence the **aim** of present research: to outline and systemize the spheres of activities of the main educational and outreach hubs and organizations in the development of jazz culture in Ukraine and assess their performance.

The most important for this research were scientific studies characterizing the ways of pop-jazz art development in Ukraine, festival and contest movements, etc., by A. Arefyeva, K. Davydovskiy, O. Zinkevych, D. Zubenko, S. Zuyev, V. Ionov, Y. Markov, V. Romanok, V. Symonenko, O. Sychova, I. Sikorska, M. Shved, and others.

Within the context of the research, the following institutions turned out to be the most effective and efficient: music houses, art agencies, producer centers and companies; public organizations and foundations; jazz projects and contests; support of Ukrainian jazz art in the framework of international cultural cooperation; various culture and art hubs; internet resources and websites; TV and radio format; activities of jazz clubs and entertainment establishments; support from the state, philanthropists, and sponsors.

Conclusions. Each of them engaged in the educational and outreach activities related to the popularization of jazz art in Ukraine depending on their specifics and abilities. They are united by the joint efforts aimed at 1) creation of the media space for jazz music; 2) shaping a steady interest to the issues of jazz culture; 3) expansion of the audience; 4) developing a high artistic taste by engaging listeners to the perception of the high-quality jazz music; 5) forming among the listeners possessing information and knowledge about jazz of the ability to assess new jazz tracks, critical view on the performance style and quality, interpretation, etc.; 6) the desire to use jazz music to reveal the creative potential of listeners as connoisseurs of jazz, etc.

Life Sciences & Earth Sciences

- Agronomy & Crop Science
- Animal Behavior & Ethology
- Animal Husbandry
- Atmospheric Sciences
- Biochemistry
- Biodiversity & Conservation Biology
- Bioinformatics & Computational Biology
- Biophysics
- Biotechnology
- Birds
- Botany
- Cell Biology
- Developmental Biology & Embryology
- Environmental & Geological Engineering
- Environmental Sciences
- Evolutionary Biology
- Ecology
- Food Science & Technology
- Forests & Forestry
- Geochemistry & Mineralogy
- Geology
- Hydrology & Water Resources
- Insects & Arthropods
- Life Sciences & Earth Sciences (general)
- Marine Sciences & Fisheries
- Microbiology
- Molecular Biology
- Mycology
- Oceanography
- Paleontology
- Pest Control & Pesticides
- Plant Pathology
- Proteomics, Peptides & Aminoacids
- Soil Sciences
- Sustainable Development
- Sustainable Energy
- Virology
- Wood Science & Technology
- Zoology

ENVIRONMENTAL PROBLEMS AND ASSIMILATION POTENTIAL OF WATER ECOSYSTEMS OF AZERBAIJAN

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Sustainable development of the agriculture is only guaranteed on the ecologically clean soils irrigated with environmentally clean waters. The purpose of this study was assessing the assimilatory potential of the river systems and the Caspian Sea's coastal waters within Azerbaijan against organic pollutants.

The biological, chemical and GIS-technologies were used to conduct the comparative evaluation of assimilation potential and self-cleaning ability of the catchment areas of the river systems and the Caspian Sea's coastal waters. The dominant role in water self-purification process from organic compounds belongs to microorganisms.

Acquired results of this study showed the assimilation potential of the country's aquatic ecosystems with respect to organic pollutants. The biogenicity and assimilation potential of the waters polluted by pesticides, oil hydrocarbons and other pollutants were determined. The negative effect of the irrigation water of the Kura River on the biogenicity and the assimilation potential of surrounded soils was revealed. The hydrocarbon nature pollutants in the country's aquatic ecosystems are decomposed much faster than synthetic pollutants. The quantity of pollutants accumulated per unit of time, transformed and purified from the water ecosystems without disrupting their normal activities was determined.

The microbial biological products were developed and proposed for bioremediation of polluted waters of the Kura River and the Caspian Sea.

MODERN WAYS OF PREVENTING ANTHRAX DISEASE

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Anthrax – one of the most dangerous diseases of animals and people, which is characterized by acute flow, sepsis, intoxication of the body, the emergence of carbuncles and high mortality.

The disease is widespread on all continents of the globe and causes significant damage to the economy of individual states. The analysis of the epizootic situation regarding anthrax in Ukraine from 1999 to 2018 shows that during this period, 69 hot spots. The threat of the disease is permanent, since there are more than 11,000 burial of animals killed by anthrax on the territory of Ukraine. The spores of the B. anthracis agent persist in the soil for more than a century.

March 23, 2016 in the village of. Chuguev, Kharkiv region officially confirmed the isolation of B. anthracis from the carcass of pigs from the private sector, meat from which was used by 17

people who caused the disease, and in July 2017, in Sumy region, the pathogen was isolated from two dead sheeps. In 2018 eight people from Odesa region became victims of anthrax. The reason for the disease of people over the past 5 years is the lack of vaccination of animals in the private sector.

"State Center of Innovation Biotechnologies" is constantly conducting epizootic monitoring of anthrax outbreaks on the territory of Ukraine, as well as documents on the location burial of animals killed by anthrax. A significant scientific achievement of the Center's scientists is the study of the biology of anthrax and the development of a method for extraction of bacilli from the objects of study, identification and receipt of their exotoxins. The extracellular toxins B. anthracis are the basis for new experimental drugs that create an alternative to the use of live spore vaccines in the case of anthrax outbreaks. The extracellular toxins B. anthracis have significant advantages over traditional vaccines: non-toxic, harmless, and have no limitations in categories such as age and animal type.

Relevant Topicality. In the territory of Ukraine, due to hostilities, a significant number of burial of animals killed by anthrax in the East and South remain uncontrolled. Particularly acute is the issue of ensuring the biological safety of the population and animals.

Methods. Studies are conducted on the extraction of B. anthracis spores, the production of exotoxin B. anthracis, the production of a specific anthrax antigen for the diagnosis of the disease.

Results The best result from the diffusion of spores from different soils is the disk-precipitation (RDP) reaction, which was modified by A. I. Zaviryukha, to optimize the methods of diagnosis of anthrax. Also, modern molecular methods, namely, PCR, are effective.

The use of experimental batches containing the exotoxin B. anthracis in laboratory animals and cattle have positive results. The drug prevents the onset of the disease and creates a long-term immunity against anthrax (up to 8 months), and in the case of experimental infection of an animal, the use of the drug helps to heal the animal and reduce the cost of antibacterial drugs.

The drug can be applied to all types of animals: agricultural, fur and wild.

Conclusions

1. Maintain a stable epizootic situation in Ukraine with regard to anthrax, it is necessary to conduct continuous monitoring of the disease.

2. Develop a common protocol for isolating anthrax spores from the soil, the environment, animal carcasses.

3. Introduce into production a preparation made from B. anthracis life products, which, in experimental testing, has a high immuno-biological, stimulating and preventive effect.

ASSESSMENT OF THE ASSIMILATION POTENTIAL OF THE SOILS OF THE BIOCLIMATIC LANDSCAPE ZONES OF AZERBAIJAN IN RELATION TO ORGANIC POLLUTIONS

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Keisurukhskaya Fatima Shamil,

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Much of the territory of Azerbaijan is contaminated with organic and inorganic substances. Low level of self-cleaning ability of the environment is determined by such factors as climate aridity, low weight of the ecosystem, low natural biodiversity, which determines a high level of sensitivity to pollution, low reproductive capacity for oxygen - only 0.8 million tons / year, poor vegetation cover (coverage of natural ephemeral vegetation only in spring and autumn), rising groundwater levels (over the past 20 years by 5-15 m), low

bioclimatic potential, highly mineralized, polluted water bodies, characteristic unstable relationship between the individual components in landscapes, lack of mutual compensation between them. As shown by historical experience, the preservation of the assimilation potential of natural landscapes in Azerbaijan is the most problematic task of nature management.

Obvious is the fact that this resource is not easy socio-economic assessments, due to the complexity of its quantitative measurement. Therefore, it is necessary to study the assimilation abilities of the soil cover of the country in order to decide promising areas of effective nature management and the development of organic farming in the future.

For a full-fledged solution of these tasks, comprehensive studies are needed to identify the actual assimilation potential of the country's natural landscapes, as well as the factors that determine the assimilation capacity of the soil cover of various bioclimatic landscapes, as one of the main components of the country's ecosystems.

The objectives of such a forecast are the complex differentiation of the territory of Azerbaijan according to the types of soil change under the influence of pollution. The tasks of zoning include identifying natural-economic areas that differ in the level of resistance to man-made loads, the ability of the environment to assimilate organic pollutants, the degree of reversibility of changes determine the nature and degree of danger of these changes for each type of area using the principle of landscape-territorial differentiation.

A four-stage system of taxonomic units for zoning the territory of Azerbaijan has been developed to assess the assimilation potential of soils in various bioclimatic landscape zones through a systematic analysis of abiotic and biotic factors that form the assimilation capacity and together determine the potential for self-purification.

The obtained results can serve as a scientific base for assessing the assimilation capacity of Azerbaijan's ecosystems — an indicator of the maximum dynamic capacity of the quantity of pollutants that can be accumulated per unit of time, destroyed, transformed and brought out of the country's ecosystems without disrupting its normal activities, as well as the methodological basis for developing programs and concepts for scientifically-based regulation and nature management in various soil-climatic zones of Azerbaijan.

THE INFLUENCE OF DISPERSANTS TO THE FLUID LOSS CONTROL AGENTS OF THE CEMENT SLURRY

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Orynbayev Seitzhan Aueszhanovich**

It is known that various technologies for insulation of water-bearing beds and enhanced oil recovery technologies are being developed to solve existing problems. However, at the same time, relatively little attention is paid to the problems of improving the quality of well cementing. Although above problems are the results of poor primary cementing of wells. Therefore, there is a huge necessity to improve technique and technology as well as backfills aimed to provide high quality and durable insulation of wells. In general, in order to obtain high quality well casing, it is inevitable to adjust the basic properties of cement mortars with the help of various chemical reagents. Herewith, in plugging material most often require correction of filtration characteristics (water loss and dehydration)

Our studies have led us to reagents such as BIIK-402, ИАК and Wellfix (P100)

The result of studies of BIIK-402 and the experience of its use in attaching wells showed the effectiveness of this reagent relative to the filter loss quality of the cement solution. However, the only

drawback of this reagent was that it is produced only in liquid form, and the insufficiently high concentration of the active substance in the liquid leads to its high consumption. One of the analogs of BIK-402 is cationic polyelectrolyte (PIAK), produced under the trademark Praestol in a powder form.

At the first stage, the effect of cationic polyelectrolyte PIAK on the main technological properties of the cement mortar was studied. However, in laboratory studies, the above works were carried out at a temperature of 25 ° C and at atmospheric pressure.

Notwithstanding we continued laboratory studies to learn the effect of this polyelectrolyte on the property of cement mortars at high temperatures like 85 °C.

After analyzing the effect of various brands of dispersant ReoTeck on the pumpability of cement mortar at high temperatures, we conclude about using of high-temperature dispersant. During the further experiments, together with the dispersant ReoTeck8500S in the obtained composition the dispersant Wellfix (P100) was used.

According to the work performed, we can draw the following conclusions:

The fluid loss additive BIK - 402 showed good results with a decrease in fluid loss and flowability of cement slurry. However, this fluid loss additive is presented in liquid form, which causes difficulties during transportation and in the preparation of cement mortar.

The PIAK fluid loss additive led to a decrease in fluid loss, increased compressive and bending strength, reduced water loss of the cement mortar, and did not lose its flowability.

PIAK fluid loss additive is compatible with other additives introduced into cement mortars for complex regulation of their properties. Also PIAK in combination with other additives improves the properties of cement mortar and cement stone.

We can use PIAK as fluid loss additive of cement slurries for HT conditions, however we have to use additional dispersant Wellfix (P100).

ENVIRONMENTALLY FRIENDLY TECHNOLOGY FOR PROCESSING INDIVIDUAL PEEL AND INDIVIDUAL SEEDS OR STRAW OF FRUITS REMAINING AFTER POMEGRANATE JUICE

Samir Hafizov,

master, head of the laboratory

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Due to the competition in the world markets of pomegranate juice that has intensified in recent years, some of its Azerbaijani enterprises producing pomegranate juice gave up their traditional markets to competing firms and began to conduct their business with the expectation of the profit from the sale of not only pomegranate juice, but also other canned goods.

Only AZNAR from Gokchay, as befits a specialized leader enterprise, is trying to find a way out of this situation due to the increasing involvement in the processing of juice waste and the production of value-added products from them. Here they study the proposals of well-known foreign firms for the transition to a "green" (clean) processing process.

It is so accepted everywhere in the post-Soviet space - to look for the technology they need only there, "far beyond the ocean", or, at worst, in Europe.

But what can they offer there abroad, besides the variant of the technology for processing the peel and seeds at two different sites with the receipt of polyphenolic extract from the peel and oil — from seeds (in the spirit of the resource-intensive technology used by

the American company STIEBS)? Maybe, the factory workers will choose another option, designed to obtain an extract from pomegranates called Pomanox (patent holder - NutraIngredients, USA) - the product of grinding and extracting pomegranates entirely without separating them into juice and hard parts?

Both of these options, in our understanding, are “extreme”, as they stand to the left and to the right at the largest distance from our version of technology. The first one is diverse, connected with the need to build completely different from each other in the instrumental and technological design of the two production sites, so its place is on the very edge of, say, the left flank. And the second option went too far to the right, because it means the release of the extract, instead of the pomegranate juice, loved by all of us. And both of them are designed to use only the soluble part of the raw material. But how can you be content with this at a time when the sharply increased competition in the world market of pomegranate juice, as well as the requirements for resource conservation, make it important to create workable multi-product production of continuous type, the main stage of which is a flexible system of gradual deepening of the processing process?

Our technology fully meets the requirements of projected savings and ecology. For us, the insoluble residue is not new waste, but another opportunity to expand the range of products with the natural force of pomegranate. We do not need two sites for the processing of individual skin and individual seeds. We need only one site for their joint processing without residue.

If we proceed from the expected results in the stage of commercial implementation of a new technology, they are so optimistic that the problem it solves may not seem like a problem at all, but one of the rare opportunities to make big money.

Today in the world each year they receive about 300 thousand tons of pomegranate juice and about 350 thousand tons of waste, the processing of which according to the technology we offer can ensure the production of pomegranate ingredients worth \$ 3 billion.

CANNING OF PERSIMMON FRUITS: HURMA FRUITS: APPROACHES AND TECHNOLOGIES

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The experience accumulated to date in the field of processing persimmon fruits shows that the people involved in this work, trying to accomplish anything, continue to do the same thing as before, which does not satisfy them. They are trying to "do better", but it turns out all the same, running in a familiar circle. Farmers want to donate a non-standard part of the persimmon crop to canneries, but she is not accepted. There is only one reason - the lack of technologies suitable for processing persimmon into high-quality canned food, beverages, dried fruits not only in Azerbaijan, but also, we can confidently say, all over the world. For a qualitative change in technology, it was necessary to solve inventive tasks, i.e. such tasks the means of solving, means of cannot solution which be found in the technical literature, are not embodied in rules, techniques, recommendations, etc., known to a qualified engineer. According to the results of this work, we obtained a patent for a method of obtaining a dry

product with the organoleptic properties of raisins and the corresponding fruit salad (RU 2552360. 2015) and another patent for a method for producing a beverage with the texture of clarified juice (RU 2645969. 2017). The first of them allows you to dry persimmon for the entire time of its consumer maturity, which comes after a short period of storage, when it acquires the best taste and, at the same time, loses its original hardness. This is the main difference between our method and the analogue methods RU 2461203. 2012 and RU 2410957.2013, designed for cutting persimmon into 1.5 mm thick slices, drying the slices and further processing the dried slices to produce chips or popcorn. The persimmon must be of a sufficiently dense consistency, so you can cut it into such small slices without disturbing their original independence. The use of persimmon dense texture does not provide for the accumulation of substances causing high organoleptic properties of the product. Its quality decreases due to the high content of coarse fibers and tart groups of polyphenols. The realization that it will be difficult to achieve high production results in those 2-3 post-harvest weeks, while the persimmon consistency remains quite dense, reflects badly on the demand for technology. Whereas our solution allows us to process completely ripe persimmon until March of the next year and receive from it a dry product with a memorable appearance and unforgettable taste, which will become a favorite delicacy among gourmets. In both of our patents, can be used a non-standard small-fruited part of the crop as a raw material, the sale of which with the benefit of itself is so much desired by Azerbaijani and other farmers.

ОПЫТНОЕ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЕ КИНЕТИКИ ПРОЦЕССА РАЗЛОЖЕНИЯ ФОСФАТА

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В связи с всесторонним развитием сельского хозяйства появилась большая необходимость получения удобрений с основными питательными элементами. В настоящее время на определение сырьевой базы и ее расширение для производства этих удобрений обращается большое внимание. Разработка более усовершенствованной технологической схемы для производства названных удобрений, также имеет важное значение. Известно, что в направлении получения фосфорных удобрений из фосфоросодержащих соединений выполнены многочисленные работы, но на сегодняшний день данный вопрос все еще остается актуальным.

Известно, что метод получения фосфорных удобрений с составом определенной усвояемости P_2O_5 , а так же получение фосфорной кислоты, остается все еще традиционный, т.е. является реакция серной кислоты с фосфоросодержащими минеральными соединениями. Анализы выполненных работ показали, что кинетика процесса разложения фосфатного сырья при наличии серной кислоты до сих пор изучена недостаточно. С целью выяснения данного вопроса в статье представлены результаты проведенных исследований.

С целью повышения степени разложения фосфатного сырья и увеличения скорость всего процесса, до настоящего времени проведены многочисленные исследования, в том числе и наши исследования. В наших исследованиях использован

апатитовый концентрат как фосфорно-содержащее минеральное соединение и серная кислота. Процесс осуществляется в двух этапах по нижеследующим реакциям:

Опытным путем определены концентрации всех компонентов в течение 140 минут в различных моментах и выявилась зависимость изменения концентрации от времени.

Изучение процесса разложения фосфорносодержащего минерального соединения с серной кислотой, выполнено при температурах 500С, 600С и 650С.

Опыты проводились при разных температурах режимах. Результаты проведены в табл.1, 2, 3 и рис. 2, 3, 4. Как видно из опытных данных I этап процесса при температуре 500С завершается в течение 40 мин. На этом этапе при разложении фосфорно-минерального соединения и серной кислотой образуется фосфорная кислота. С течением времени уменьшается концентрация фосфорно-минерального соединения и серной кислоты в связи их расходом по первой реакции. При полном расходе серной кислоты концентрация фосфорной кислоты, на полученной I стадии достигает своего максимума. В этот момент завершается образование сульфата кальция и ее концентрация также достигается своего максимума. Таким образом завершается I стадия процесса. На II стадии процесса начинается реакция взаимодействия фосфорно-минерального соединения с фосфорной кислотой и с течением времени в системе уменьшается концентрация фосфорной кислоты. На этом этапе образуется суперфосфат в виде продукта и начинается увеличение его концентрации в системе. До конца процесса продолжается увеличение концентрации в системе, полученной в виде побочного продукта HF. А основной продукт получается в начале II этапа - На 41-ой минуте.

В результате определено, что при температуре 500С I этап процесса происходит в течение 40 мин, а при температуре 600С и 650С- всего за 10 мин. Следовательно во II и III случаях скорость I этапа процесса гораздо выше по сравнению I случаем. II этап процесса является лимитирующей стадией процесс; сам процесс во всех случаях происходит идентичным образом, только отличаются параметры во времени, а закономерности остаются одними и теми же.

ПОЛУЧЕНИЕ ИЗОБУТАНА И ИЗОБУТИЛЕНА ВЫСОКОЙ ЧИСТОТЫ ИЗ ПИРОЛИЗНОГО ГАЗА

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В промышленности изобутилен получается из изобутан-изобутиленовой фракции пиролизного газа. Этот процесс осуществляется экстракцией серной кислотой на установке

Метод извлечения изобутана и изобутилена из изобутан-изобутиленовой фракции пиролизного газа, продолжает находиться в эксплуатации, во многих развитых странах.

В тезисе приведены результаты исследований процесса получения изобутана и изобутилена высокой чистоты из изобутан-изобутиленовой фракции пиролизного газа. Получение изобутана и изобутилена из изобутан-изобутиленовой фракции пиролизного

газа проведены экстракцией серной кислотой с последующей очисткой адсорбционным методом изобутановой фракции от изобутилена, а изобутиленовой фракции от н-бутиленов. Для этого в существующую установку были введены блоки адсорбции, установленные соответственно на выходе изобутановой и изобутиленовой фракций. В качестве адсорбентов были выбраны активированный уголь AP-3 для очистки изобутановой фракции от изобутилена и цеолит СаА для очистки изобутиленовой фракции от н-бутиленов.

Результаты исследований процесса получения изобутана и изобутилена высокой чистоты из изобутан-изобутиленовой фракции пиролизного газа. Получение изобутана и изобутилена из изобутан-изобутиленовой фракции пиролизного газа проведены экстракцией серной кислотой с последующей очисткой адсорбционным методом изобутановой фракции от изобутилена, а изобутиленовой фракции от н-бутиленов. Для этого в существующую установку были введены блоки адсорбции, установленные соответственно на выходе изобутановой и изобутиленовой фракций. В качестве адсорбентов были выбраны активированный уголь AP-3 для очистки изобутановой фракции от изобутилена и цеолит СаА для очистки изобутиленовой фракции от н-бутиленов.

Следовательно, совмещение процессов экстракции и адсорбции, с использованием адсорбентов-активированного угля AP-3 для очистки изобутановой фракции от изобутилена и цеолита СаА для очистки изобутиленовой фракции от н-бутиленов, и введением в технологическую установку блоков адсорбции позволяет увеличить степень извлечения изобутана и изобутилена из изобутан-изобутиленовой фракции пиролизного газа практически до 100%. Полученные изобутан и изобутилен высокой чистоты, отвечают современным требованиям технологических процессов.

Проведены исследования и разработана технология процесса получения высокочистого изобутилена и изобутана из изобутан-изобутиленовой фракции пиролизного газа. С этой целью для очистки изобутановой фракции от примеси изобутилена подобран адсорбент марки AP-3, а для очистки изобутиленовой фракции от примеси н-бутиленов подобран цеолит марки СаА и проведены адсорбционные очистки. Благодаря высокой избирательной способности и активности этих адсорбентов по отношению к данным примесям получена степень чистоты изобутилена и изобутана 99,9%.

Процесс экстракция и адсорбция, введение в существующую установку блоков адсорбции, позволяет увеличить степень извлечения изобутана и изобутилена из изобутан-изобутиленовой фракции пиролизного газа.

Для осуществления указанных процессов в существующую в производстве установку, внедрены две адсорбционные блоки, тем самым получена новая модифицированная технологическая схема.

В результате исследований разработана технология получения изобутана и изобутилена высокой чистоты из изобутан-изобутиленовой фракции пиролизного газа. Для очистки изобутановой фракции от изобутилена был выбран активированный уголь AP-3, а изобутиленовой фракции от н-бутиленов- цеолит СаА, благодаря высокой избирательной способности которых получены изобутан и изобутилен высокой чистоты (99,9% - 99,9%). Добавлены в существующую установку блоков адсорбции, которые установлены соответственно на выходе изобутановой и изобутиленовой фракций. Установлено, что совмещение процессов экстракции и адсорбции и введение в существующую установку блоков адсорбции, позволяет увеличить степень извлечения изобутана и изобутилена из изобутан-изобутиленовой фракции пиролизного газа.

Social Sciences

- Academic & Psychological Testing
- African Studies & History
- Anthropology
- Archaeology
- Architecture
- Asian Studies & History
- Bioethics
- Canadian Studies & History
- Chinese Studies & History
- Cognitive Science
- Criminology, Criminal Law & Policing
- Development Economics
- Diplomacy & International Relations
- Early Childhood Education
- Economic History
- Education
- Educational Administration
- Educational Psychology & Counseling
- Educational Technology
- Environmental & Occupational Medicine
- Environmental Law & Policy
- Epistemology & Scientific History
- Ethics
- European Law
- Family Studies
- Feminism & Women's Studies
- Forensic Science
- Geography & Cartography
- Health Policy & Medical Law
- Higher Education
- History
- Human Migration
- Human Resources & Organizations
- International Law
- Law
- Library & Information Science
- Middle Eastern & Islamic Studies
- Military Studies
- Paleontology
- Political Science
- Public Health
- Public Policy & Administration
- Science & Engineering Education
- Sex & Sexuality
- Social Sciences (general)
- Social Work
- Sociology
- Special Education
- Sustainable Development
- Teaching & Teacher Education
- Technology Law
- Urban Studies & Planning

ISSUES OF INCREASING THE POLITICAL ACTIVITY OF CITIZENS IN THE SOCIETY

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Today, we are working on building a strong civil society. Everyone in the community must act to build a strong state.

Due to a number of domestic and foreign sources of political activism in the democratization of public life, it has become clear that, increasing the activeness of civil society institutions in increasing the political activity of citizens, first of all, strengthening their financial sources, ensuring that citizens actively participate in various political processes through the Internet, and the development of criteria that determine the level of political activity of its citizens.

It is expedient to carry out a number of activities to enhance political activism in the democratization process of society:

- raising the level of employment of citizens in the community;
- It is important for the people to actively participate in political processes and to form a high level of public awareness of the current economic, social, political, and processes of the modern society by raising the public's high responsibility, political and legal culture. First of all, it is necessary to create a social, political, organizational and legal mechanism, including the establishment and financial support of political and social analysis centers for the study of such issues in order to study and address existing socio-political problems in the country;
- Using the electronic electoral system, establishing a digital system in the entire system, e-democracy, using social networking and other online channels;
- Poverty and unemployment are high in society, whereas the level of citizens' support for political activities may be lower or against the existing political system, so it is necessary to improve the welfare of the population,
- Ensuring equality before the law and equality of all citizens in society increases the political, social and political responsibility of citizens to support the rule of law.
- raising the role of civil society institutions in raising the political awareness of citizens, insofar as civil society institutions are able to address citizens' concerns so far as they support citizens;

Creation of special programs and organizational and legal frameworks for exchanging views, problems, suggestions and comments by political parties and MPs using Internet networks;

For the active participation of citizens in political processes, first of all, social resources should be available to citizens, and social resources are influenced by the literacy, the availability of income, the status and influence of the society, as well as the age and gender of citizens.

A civil society activist, along with himself, follows the members of the community, and through the democratic institutions of society, solves the needs and interests of collective groups.

Based on world experience, based on the criteria that determine the level of political activity, it is necessary to introduce a practice of continuous researches of political activity in the society and to identify the system of measures based on the results, as well as to report to the general public on the findings.

BETWEEN TWO FIRES: TOTALITARIAN SYSTEMS OF NAZI GERMANY AND SOVIET UNION IN LITERARY REPRESENTATION OF UKRAINIAN WRITER MYKOLA SMOLENCHUK

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Mykola Smolenchuk is a writer, who masterfully developed the theme of WWII horrors and postwar period as seen by a Slavonic personality, first and foremost he did it in his autobiographical novel “The Grey-haired Generation”, which belongs the special heritage of my native land – Kirovograd region of Ukraine.

The novel has an interesting style of the narration: the reader perceives events of the plot only through the eyes of the main character – a teenager named Victor. So, we are conversant only in that facts, that he knows. Such method provides an exceptional level of realism and involvement in the world of the book, allows a deep penetration into the consciousness of the main character and promotes the formation of an empathic connection between him and the reader.

A great merit of “The Grey-haired Generation” is not only an unveiling of the tragedy of the nations of Central and Eastern Europe and the republics of the USSR, occupied and oppressed by the Nazis, but of the tragedy of the German people as well, who were also deceived by the Nazi regime. Another important feature of the novel is a description of the description of hardships, encountered by many nations in the SU, including Ukrainians, after the liberation from the Nazi occupation.

For lots of Soviet people the aggressive Nazi policies have created difficult life circumstances ranging from rigors of occupation to forceful deportation to Germany, which meant hard work in the best case and “death camps” in the worst. That is why the DPs perceived the Soviets as true liberators. The truth lies in the fact, that in many aspects the policies and practical actions of the Soviet government closely resembled those of the Nazi regime, so “the liberated” soon found themselves under pressure of another totalitarianism, this time – the Soviet power.

During the war, Victor was forced to work as an Ostarbeiter. After a while, he attempted to escape across the whole of Germany, eventually, he was being eventually captured and sent into a penalty camp. But the greatest shock that he felt during these events was caused by the betrayal and deception of the Soviet Union power: after liberation, he was sent not to the Soviet army, as the “liberators” said, but to a concentration camp: without investigation and trial, a lot of still able-bodied people had been accused of Nazi-collaborating and were sent to “atone their guilt”. Thus, the Soviet Union received a cheap labor force, which in terrible conditions had to work hard for the benefit of the restoration and establishment of the postwar Soviet state.

One should note here, that Victor, who concentrated in himself the author's beliefs, is a person who passionately believed in the ideals of the Soviet state. So, the novel allows us to follow this process of enlightenment – from naive devotion to discovering a hidden side of the Soviet Union and becoming aware of its totalitarian character as well.

RESEARCH OF HISTORY OF CONSTRUCTION OF KREMENCHUG HYDROPOWER STATION

Oleg BABENKO

During 2013-2018, mostly on the basis of documents of the State Archives of Kirovograd region, we studied the history of KPS construction; research resulted in three monographs and a number of articles, which provide a basis for certain conclusions.

KPS was erected as the most powerful element of a chain of HPS on the Dnieper in the situation of drastic budget funds saving, conditioned by tasks of restoring Ukrainian economics after WWII and developing USSR industrial potential. Soviet industry leaders were primarily guided by low-priced electricity and a chance to obtain a mechanism for regulating Dnieper flow to optimize work of Dnieper HPS.

To save the money and to speed up the construction a granite base of a promontory near the village of Taburische 12 km from Kremenchug was chosen as HPS construction site.

The government ignored threats of transformational changes of socio-economical character in the region.

The town of Novogeorgievsk was to be in the basin, 186 other settlements from three regions of Ukraine – in the flood zone. Their inhabitants were relocated to neighbouring villages and to “New city” and “New Village”, which never became “sample” and “Communist” in nature due to problems, conditioned by inadequate placement and low quality of construction of living quarters and infrastructure objects.

Protective dams erected near Cherkassy and Kremenchug caused considerable additional expenditure.

Along with settlements the flood zone also covered numerous industrial enterprises and cooperatives, vast expanses of arable land, pastures and forests, mineral resources cites, cemeteries and churches, small electric power stations, roads and railways, wire lines, etc. Attempts at saving led only to overspending.

Other kinds of expenditure were not considered.

The category of replaced persons included 80281 dwellers of Cherkassy, 35352 – of Poltava, 15439 – of Kirovograd regions.

Problems with replacing buildings and erecting new ones, paying compensations, providing dwellings for the seniors and the disabled came up. Poor quality of organizing living conditions for locals also caused the same excess expenditure as in HPS construction.

Project mistakes, “storm” work, permanent drawbacks in work, shortage of construction materials and pilfering of those available, growth of financial costs, qualified labour force shortage, lack of mechanisms, frequent workers’ strikes and rigorous reaction of KGB to them – all marked the character and tempo of construction.

Work was conducted under conditions of unorganized everyday living conditions: absence of work clothes and footwear, roughness of leaders, unjust methods of evaluating work results. Greater part of those problems had been overcome, but it also caused increased construction costs.

Technological innovations speeded up the construction, bringing in greater costs.

Remaking the Dnieper landscape caused environmental problems.

Irreparable damage, inflicted to historic and cultural heritage in the flood zone; caused loss of archaeological artifacts, historical objects and locations.

Conclusions: chase for cheap electricity proved expensive for Ukraine, as this construction was politically motivated, it ignored direct and indirect material losses and moral sufferings of thousands of persons, and assisted quick career growth for representatives of new, post-Stalin generation of Soviet technocracy and Partocracy.

ETHNIC FACTOR IN CONFLICT

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Ethnic conflict is the cause of the ongoing war in the world. (Washington, DC: US Institute of Peace, 2000. Saideman, Stephen M. *The Ties That Divide* Columbia, 2001. Horowitz, Donald L. *Ethnic Groups* 1940. Rothchild, Donald. *Managing Ethnic Conflict in Africa: Pressures and Incentives for Cooperation* Washington, DC: Brookings, 1997. Chua, Amy *World on Fire: How Exporting Free Market Democracy Breeds Ethnic Hatred and Global Instability* New York: Doubleday, 2003. Williams, Robin M. *The Wards Within: People and States in Conflict*. Cornell, 2003). Ethnic group is a group of people who have shared heritage, language, culture or religious ties, as well as common identity. In many cases, the conflicts between ethnic groups are materially tangible, mainly formed around the territories and control of government. The cause of the ethnic conflict can be the hatred of one ethnic group towards the other. (Cederman, Lars-Erik. *Emergent Actors in World Politics: How States and Nations Develop and Dissolve* Princeton, 1997). The aim of ethnic groups is to obtain statehood, which is itself related to the desire to rule the area in which they live. The borders of the state often do not coincide with the area occupied by a particular ethnic group. Consequently, members of one ethnic group often live in territorial borders belonging to other ethnic groups, and sometimes even the majority, which is often the cause of the conflict. For example, in 1974 on the island of Cyprus following the pro-Greek coup, Turkish troops were deployed to the north of the island in the area inhabited by Turks. The island's government controlled the Greek settlement. UN peacekeepers have been providing peace in the conflict zones for 30 years, and the problem is still unsolved even though Cyprus is a member of the European Union and Turkey is seeking to join it (Carment David, *The International Dimensions of Ethnic Conflict: Concepts, Indicators and Theory*, JPR, vol.30, no.2, 1993, pp.137-150). The current situation confirms the complex nature and destructive power of the ethnic conflict. Unlike the above-mentioned ethnic groups, other ones do not have their own states. For example, Kurds living in Turkey, Iraq, Syria and Iran do not have their own state and are trying to create a state of Kurdistan, they are trying to control a part of the territory of these states in order to create their own state. (Barkey, Henry J., and Graham E. Fuller. *Turkey's Kurdish Question*: Lanham, MD: Rowman @ Littlefield)

In the ethnic conflict, in many cases, the parties are trying to change the territorial boundaries established by force. The former Soviet republics, Moldova, are inhabited by ethnic Romanians, but in the eastern part of Moldova, far from Romania, There are residents ethnic group of Russians, who represent ethnic minorities. In 1991, after the declaration of Moldova as an independent state, the process of restoration of national identity began in the Romanian population. The Citizens of Romania with the Russian nationality decided to allocate it and to move the international borders as a result of the armed conflict. When ethnic groups living in the controlled territory of the country are a minority, this ethnic group is often the subject of discrimination and ultimately the object of expulsion. In some of the former colonies, whose borders are arbitrarily determined, some ethnic groups live in the territory of two or more states, and in other states, different ethnic groups are living in one state and are historically hostile towards one another. For example, there are 250 ethnic groups in Nigeria, the largest of them two Muslim ethnic groups in the north and two Christian groups live in the south. The recent developments in Nigeria and the diversity of Nigerian ethnicity in the near future tend to be a Nigerian-registered tendency, as well as the old conflict traces, which impede political stability. (Eriksen HT *Linguistic Hegemony and Minority Resistance*, vol, 29, no.3, 1992, pp.313 -332)

There were effective leverage to control ethnic conflicts during the strict system of alliances with the Cold War and authoritarian Communist power. In the USSR and Yugoslavia, within the united strong state, which was always ready to restrict the interests of the local population, it could be said, that the disagreements on the ethnic basis among the population of the different nationalities in neighboring areas were preserved. After the disintegration of the Communist system, there were religious and ethnic conflicts that were on the background of violence and armed confrontation. (Forsberg Tuomas, Territorial changes and International conflict, JPR, Nov 1, 1992. pp. 465-466)

ABOUT TECHNOLOGIES USED FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF ELECTRONIC MULTIMEDIA TEXTBOOKS AND THEIR APPLICATION IN THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS

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These days, it's almost impossible to solve the problems facing the education system, without the use of modern technologies for informatization of education, which serve as highly effective tools for providing tutors with an opportunity to intensify students' learning activities and stimulate their cognitive interest.

One of the vivid examples for modern multimedia educational resource is an electronic multimedia textbook.

There is a huge variety of technologies and ready-made software products that allow you to develop electronic textbooks. We would like to represent the electronic textbook, called "Modifiers of the program 3ds Max, Essence and Classification". We have used the technology of Flash and the object-oriented programming language Action Script for developing the aforesaid electronic textbook. The latest has been designed as a book with scrolling pages. The first page of the book contains the content of the tutorial. As soon as the desired content item is activated, the page is turned over and the corresponding training material opens. The book provides with details of the commonly used modifiers in the 3ds Max program, and facilitates the perception of the functionality of each modifier. In the electronic textbook, there have included video tutorials to demonstrate not only how a particular modifier works, but also the ways by which the specific modifier can be applied when creating a three-dimensional model of an object. The electronic textbook also includes test questions, as well as a variety of tasks for independent work, and a Flash game. All these enable to repeat the basic points of the material studied in an easier and more efficient way.

The modern web technologies such as HTML, JavaScript, CSS, and PHP are also widely used to develop multimedia electronic textbooks.

We have developed and applied in education an electronic textbook, called "Creating three-dimensional animations in 3ds Max", by using web technologies. The electronic textbook contains theoretical educational materials and practical tasks, as well as images, animations, video and audio information, and links that contribute to find additional information related to the main terms of the textbook quicker. After each chapter of the electronic textbook there are questions and tasks specifically designed for independent work. The practical exercises contain methodical recommendations and video tutorials for students, which guide them to perform the demonstrated actions, which help creating elements of three-dimensional animation in 3ds Max environment.

Although it is already obvious that the aforesaid electronic multimedia textbooks are didactic tools in practice that significantly increase the effectiveness in teaching the basics of modeling three-dimensional objects within 3ds Max environment, we have developed educational resource, in which electronic textbooks of this specialization are gathered. The student has an opportunity to study the specific electronic textbook which he/she is interested in.

The educational resource has been developed with Microsoft Visual Studio 2017, the .NET Core Runtime 2.0.6 version has been used, DevExtreme framework styles have been set up with the Bootstrap 4 toolkit, and database has been drawn up in the Microsoft SQL Server 2017 system.

To conclude, only the systemized approach of learning and the using innovative educational technologies will increase the effectiveness of the entire educational process.

INNOVATIVE PEDAGOGICAL APPROACHES TO TRAINING OF THE PROFESSIONAL DENTISTS: METHOD OF "COMPETITIVE GROUPS"

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Today's medical community has outlined new trends. In the medical community improving are directed at improving the quality of education of doctors, in particular dentists, necessitates the individualization of the educational process with the active position of the physician's personality in the process of mastering the subject. By our previous studies the positive experience of the implementation of a number of innovative methods in the educational process was proved in particular the method of "competitive groups", "case method", "report and discussion", "brainstorming" and others.

The purpose of this work is to investigate the effectiveness of application of the method of "competitive groups" in the training of dentists. The main characteristics include: methodological provision ; competent approach. The educational tasks of the "competitive groups" method develop theoretical and practical skills; theoryanalysis to solve practical problems; improve communication skills to formulate questions and requests; develop the ability use multiple approaches to the implementation of the action plan; form the ability to comprehensively analysis the situation and make a decision, develop prognosis skills and critical thinking.

To achieve the goal, 3 study groups of 10 people each were formed. For Groups I and II, the "competitive groups" study was chosen as the active learning method. Both groups had almost the same theoretical knowledge and expressive motivation to study.

In Group III, "report and discussion" method was used. It was done low confidence of the dentists about their own abilities and, as a result, a low motivational component, resalting in fear about of more "successful" groups.

As a result of the application of the "competitive groups" method group I and II , a significant desire was to be competitive. Thus, as a result of Group II was able to overcome its insufficient self-esteem. Both groups were not only able to assess the global nature of the presented problem, but also expressed and stated their own, independent point of view. During our research each group demonstrated their readiness to cooperate in order to achieve the goal.

It should be noted, that at the first stage of the study , the "report and discussion" method was not effectivel as it was supposed to be in Group III. Low theoretical knowledge and low self-esteem made it impossible to find the right path to the goal. Step by step, the majority in this group were able to overcome shyness and participate more actively in the discussion.

Despite certain difficulties during the discussion, the professional dentists felt more confident and could overcome difficulties in their studies. Thus, due to "report and discussion" method the philosophy on the perception of the learning process by Group III greatly changed.

SMALL CULTURES, LANGUAGE AND NATIONAL IDENTITY

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Globalization is a process that started much earlier than the term that defines it. The desire for a world-wide mastery, the expansion of territories by some country or its leader and the spread of culture are all signs of globalization, familiar to mankind since the days of Ancient Egypt and Alexander the Great.

Nowadays, the process of globalization has transformed, became less territory-dependent and more sophisticated in terms of technology; nevertheless the essence of this phenomenon remains the same: large states dominate the world processes – in modern world primarily due to more advanced information technologies. Small states and small cultures a priori are in a losing situation; because of weaker economics they cannot produce the necessary amount of competing information in national languages. Modern young people mainly consume media products targeted at global auditorium, as a result only two decades of active Internet using we can definitely notice a significant decrease in the level of knowledge of the native languages and diminishing the role of the cultural context in national societies. Finally, in global context, losing small cultures will affect big ones too.

Small states need to develop and implement a consistent policy of protection and development of national languages as the most important component of preserving their national culture and identity. One of the main directions of policy aimed on reserving traditional unique values of smaller cultures may be seen in producing -firstly for children - quality media products in national languages.

PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE IN MEDICAL EDUCATION: THE PROBLEM OF PSYCHOLOGICAL TRAINING

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The problem of studying the peculiarities of the professional competence of doctors in the process of professional development and its influence on professional activity remains insufficiently investigated. We are convinced that the new vector of education at a higher medical school should be directed not only to the acquisition of professional knowledge, skills and skills, which, of course, forms the basis for the professional competence of the doctor, but also the formation of the motivational and valuable areas of the individual, becoming her as a professional, which possesses a wide range of necessary professional, personal, communicative and social competences.

It is this approach that will help make the training of a specialist truly personal-oriented, as it activates self-regulation, self-knowledge and self-realization, optimizes the activity and highlights the competence of the specialist as the main value training motive for the professional self-realization of the doctor.

The formation of the psychological competence of a future specialist is intended to change the essence of the process of mastering professional knowledge and become the basis of personal training for an independent, competitive professional activity.

According to research scientists from the analysis of current trends in the development of education in many countries, the selection and implementation of key competencies is becoming a priority methodological and didactic task.

In accordance with the concept of professional development of the person, the professionalism of the doctor includes not only the effective performance of his professional activities, but also the maturity of the personality of a specialist, a combination of professionally important qualities with psychological in the process of qualified medical interaction.

Given the specifics of the professional activities of the doctor, an important factor in its effectiveness is professional competence. The insufficient level of development of professional competences of graduates of medical universities negatively affects the effectiveness of future professional activities of a doctor.

The professional competence of a doctor is a complex of skills acquired in the process of training the knowledge, skills and abilities necessary for the performance of their professional duties. In view of this, it is reasonable to assume that the main task of education and training, the result of professional development of a specialist in a higher medical school is the formation of professional competence of medical students.

In the context of the issue that has been raised, special attention is paid to scientific researches of psychological and pedagogical orientation, as well as to the methodological problems of continuing vocational education, didactics of professional education, issues of professional readiness, and peculiarities of development and formation of future specialists in the process of professional training. A number of works are devoted to the study of the personality-professional formation of a specialist, in particular a doctor.

MODERN APPROACHES TO IN-SERVICE EDUCATION OF SCHOOL PRINCIPALS OF UKRAINE

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Preparation of school principals for professional activity in the period of social & economic changes in Ukraine, its integration into European system of education – one of the main task for the system of post graduate education. Nowadays Ukrainian scientists & practices try to develop & implement modern models of In-Service education to prepare a generation of school principals with competences of a leader of the 21st century. A variety of in-service courses, which are suggested by the Public administration & Educational management Department (Department) of University of Educational Management, based on differentiation, humanism, individual approaches, form motivation to make a career & motivate others, the possibility to solve problems, develop competences to use project management & time-management, develop initiative & business competences, skills of team work, critical thinking & competences to do the analysis, enrich the knowledge of education

economy & finance, develop competences of effective cooperation with school & local community, implement democratic school management etc. The main Department's task today is to integrate efforts of Ukrainian & European scientists in order to develop an All-Ukrainian In-service Educational Cluster as a modern model of post graduate education to satisfy the needs of school principals with different levels of professional skills: from newcomers to supervisor-practitioner with highly developed management skills. Such approach will: combine effort of initiative & advanced professors from more than 20 regional Post Graduate Educational Institutions & help many school principals to choose necessary courses, learn the best school management practice of Europe & Ukraine, give the possibility to internship at educational institutions abroad, generate new ideas & implement all the best in their schools.

PROBLEMS OF STRUGGLE WITH SOCIAL ISOLATION OF PEOPLE WITH SPECIAL NEEDS DURING ECONOMIC CRISIS IN UKRAINE

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Disablement, as a social meaning, belongs to special citizens in any country in the world. Today, the population of people with special needs among the inhabitants of the planet reaches the figure of more than a billion people or 15%. The number of people with special needs in Ukraine is about 2.9 million. Almost 80% of this population are working age persons. But, unfortunately, it's unfortunate to talk about equal opportunities for employment, adapted infrastructure and education for them. People with disabilities are not simply depend on out-of-pocket help - they are not in a position to overcome the informational, physical and psychological barriers. This state of affairs is shameful and unacceptable for a civilized European state. Because disability is not a verdict, people with special needs can and will become full-fledged and highly effective members of society, excellent specialists, socially active and cheerful people who can inspire a lot of people, including absolutely healthy members of our society.

Social policy and its impact on the implemenation of social assistance to people with various physical and mental disabilities are very important in solving this problem. Social policy on addressing the issue of people with special needs in Ukraine is at the stage of formation. Social legislation is developing, social opinion is changing. However, social policy in Ukraine, focused on the disability of adults and children, is being built today on the basis of a medical model. Such a model freely or unknowingly weaks the social position of a person with a disability, reduces its social significance, separates from society, increases its unequal social status, condemns it to recognition of its inequality, uncompetitiveness in comparison with other people. Such an approach carries a discriminatory idea, reveals the attitude of society towards persons with disabilities as a socially useless category.

In 2009, Ukraine ratified the United Nations Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities, which, together with the protocol, came into force on February 4, 2010. However, it should be noted that in the current conditions of the political and economic crisis in Ukraine, fulfillment of the undertaken obligations becomes extremely problematic.

In recent years, certain measures have been taken and a number of important legal acts aimed at realizing the rights of people with disabilities and ensuring their full participation in the life of society have been adopted. But, unfortunately, in life these laws remain so "dead".

Today, the situation of persons with disabilities, the situation in which they are in fact did not change. In today's conditions of economic instability, the people with special needs were one of the most socially vulnerable groups of the population. The main problem that requires an immediate solution is overcoming the social isolation of persons with disabilities, the limited ability to communicate with them, organizing their leisure time, studying, obtaining a profession, finding possible earnings.

Work for a people with special needs is more than an improvement in the well-being of his family; This is, first of all, the possibility of self-affirmation, self-realization, a sense of necessity for society. Socially-provided, decent life for people with disabilities can only be talked about when they are competitive in the labor market. At present, the unemployment rate among the disabled has substantially increased, it is much higher than among the healthy population, and it varies depending on many indicators - the type and groups of disability, health, age, gender. The work of people with disabilities, as a rule, is low-wage, and in spite of its loss, the legislation does not stipulate the provision of a disabled person the status of the unemployed.

It should be noted that to date, the state does not have a comprehensive strategy for the employment of people with limited functional capabilities. It is precisely the work "returns a person to life" and that is why employment is an important stage in adapting a person to a society and professional rehabilitation of people with special needs.

CONTRIBUTION OF TURKISH THOUGHTS TO THE WORLD HERITAGE

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Political revival due to the fall of the Caliphate gave a powerful impetus to the development of science, culture and art among the Turkic peoples. Emerging independent feudal states were paid attention to the development of science, enlightenment, collected advanced people in palaces, built mosques, bridges and magnificent palaces. A large number of madrasas, famous throughout the East, functioned in the cities. Primary schools studied the Quran in the mosques.

The well-known mathematician Abu Abdullah Muhammad bin Musa al-Khwarizmi wrote a number of works on astronomy, geography and mathematics. His book "Kitab ul-Jabr ve Mukabele" (Algebra) was translated into Latin. Al-Khwarizmi was the founder of not only algebra, but also trigonometry.

Al-Farabi who was the great thinker of the East, wrote numerous works on philosophy and logic. In the work "Ihsa ul-Ulim" ("Number of Sciences"), Al-Farabi gives a classification of sciences. He is considered the founder of the science of logic after Aristotle. One of the great scientists of Central Asia and the whole East was Abu Reyhan bin Muhammad al-Biruni Al-Khwarizmi (973-1048). The scientist-encyclopedist lived in Ghazna and wrote over 100 works on philosophy, history, geography, mathematics, astronomy, mineralogy, physics, etc. He proved the rotation of the Earth around the Sun the first 500 years before Copernicus.

The great scholar of the East Ibn Sina in Europe is glorified as "Avicenna." Ibn Sina wrote a 5-volume book about medicine "Al-Qanun fit-tibb" (Law of Medical Science), an

encyclopedia of philosophical works "Ash-Shafa", "Al-Fisul", etc. He was the only surgeon in the whole East and wrote 250 major works. His disciple the great Azerbaijani philosopher Bakhmanyar ibn Marzban played an essential role in the development of world philosophy.

One of the great poets of the East, whose name was included in the list of classics of world poetry, was Nizami (Ilyas) Ganjavi. The immortal "Khamsa" Nizami glorified him all over the world. He created the philosophy of an ideal state, ahead of Thomas More and Tomaso Campanella.

Mongolian campaigns and conquests in the XIII-XV centuries. caused great damage to the socio-economic and cultural life of the Turkic peoples. Meanwhile, some achievements in science and literature were noticeable. In 1259, under the leadership of the great Azerbaijani scientist with encyclopedic knowledge of Nasiraddin Tusi, an observatory was built in Maragha. After his death, this place was taken by his son Sadraddin. In this observatory worked more than a hundred scientists from many countries of the world. It was the first academy in the East. The studies carried out here and the writings that have been written form the basis of European science. The tables compiled at the Maragha Observatory were more accurate than the current five-figure geometric tables.

The book of the greatest scientist, Nasiraddin Tusi "Zij Ilkhani" ("Tables of Elkhani") very quickly became known throughout Europe. In the issues of the concept of numbers N. Tusi for 400 years ahead of European science. The book "Tahriri-Eglides" ("Interpretation of Euclid") influenced the work of prominent European scholars.

MATTER OF POLITICAL DESSICION IN STATE GOVERNANCE

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State Governance s.c. Governmental Relations which arises on one hand between the State Officials and State institutions which are the Subjects of Government and on the other hand between the Population and among the separate Groups.

The actuality of the Topic has been characterized by the Difficulties that accompanies the Management of Process, the State Governance in the modern society is highly multificated and more difficult because the Number of different State Organizations is huge. In the modern Society State Governance is regulated by the Normative Acts. It is very important to highlight the Conditions of main Factors in State Governance, which expresses „Right of legitimate violence.

The state segment is exclusively assigned to the state - administrative management. It covers all diverse governance activities carried out by executive authorities.

In modern society, it is impossible to think of important political or state outcomes, if there are some named tasks in everyday practice.

The decision making process in the team is distributed through a hierarchical principle, partial delegation of the powers of the head of the ordinary workers.

In order to make real recommendations or recommendations to be taken, it is necessary to present these information and recommendations to the public, to any

Organisations or Persons which are stakeholders or which have concrete impact on the decision-making process, From this point of view, when making decisions in state management, special importance is given to the mass media.

Information needed to receive public transmissions is provided by mass media. Media, press, radio and television are one of the most important parts of modern society. They have influence on Social life and also on State Governance. It can be said that one of the methods of state governance is the method of information advantage. Today the media is considered fair as the fourth government, which is due to their influence and impact on the object. This latter is largely determined by the direction of public opinion.

The decision is the universal form of behavior of the human and management subject, which is due to their conscious and purposeful action. Decision-making, adoption and implementation are a necessary and universal condition for normal functioning of the public.

In decision making, the subject of the political process is always trying to find an optimal option. There is no optimal solution, there is only the optimal choice. Therefore, its general purpose is the choice of alternatives.

although, The comparative optimality of the decision is largely dependent on the set of alternative models. Criterion of decision making is also important. We can say that we need comparisons for choice, and we need to have a criterion for comparison.

Thus, the main thing in state management is that each method serves the most dominant management - optimal decision making.

INTERACTION OF SOCIAL COMMUNICATIONS AND CULTURE IN THE MODERN SOCIETY

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Modern society is distinguished by the active formation of the global communication space, which significantly affects the life of society, individual personality and functioning of the components of the culture system. Such information-revolutionary changes have a unique impact on all elements of the social system and communication system. Today, information has become key to everyone's lives. So we can state the fact of the introduction of humanity into a new stage of its development - in the era of the information society with all its achievements, contradictions and conflicts.

The new stage in the development of society was caused by the next wave of the scientific and technological revolution, the development of new information and telecommunication technologies that drastically changed the way of human life, industrial relations and management methods, the system of value orientations, the style of life and the world perception of people. Global technologies change the forms of communication, and the rapid development of the Internet brings significant changes to the modern information and communication environment, social communications and culture itself.

Communication as one of the oldest institutes of society today becomes of exceptional significance - it is through communication that the entire history of mankind passes; communication forms vital values, one of which is culture.

Today, social communications are a basic component of the information society and a necessary factor for its progress. Social communication actively influences all spheres of human life, its material and spiritual culture.

In an information society, the problem of interaction between social communication and culture is central. First of all, this is due to the intensification of the information and communication space itself. After all, informatization and globalization of the modern world contributes to the dynamic development of intercultural contacts, the creation of new socio-cultural communicative entities.

The communicative value of culture is the use of certain strata of knowledge by various cultures in public. In the interaction of cultures, each borrows in the other necessary information necessary to achieve its own goal. The interaction of culture and communication in the information society is a process of interweaving of absolute and relative values as social phenomena.

The practical needs of the interaction of socio-communication and culture lead to the need for new theoretical searches, lead to a rethinking of traditional ideas and a pressing need in the corresponding scientific paradigm.

Thus, the interaction of social communications and culture serves as a complex socio-cultural process of interaction between representatives of the information society (individual individuals, social groups) among themselves, between representatives of other social or cultural groups, which is an integral and necessary component of the modern information society.

PEDAGOGICAL CONDITIONS OF FORMING THE SELF-EDUCATIONAL COMPETENCE OF THE FUTURE TEACHER OF MATHEMATICS IN THE PROFESSIONAL TRAINING PROCESS

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The research determines and substantiates theoretically the pedagogical conditions of forming the self-educational competence of the future teacher of mathematics in the process of professional training, among them: formation of the motivation of the future teacher of mathematics for self-educational competence; pedagogical stimulation of the future teacher of mathematics as a condition for the formation of self-educational competence; research activity of the future teacher of mathematics as a means of formation of self-educational competence.

Motivation of the future teachers of mathematics is an integral part of their professional motivation. Learning mathematics is not an easy work, but mathematics brings up the prudence, intellectual flexibility, logical thinking and the ability to predict certain situations in advance. And this is especially needed for everyone in market conditions.

The formation of the motivational component of the self-educational competence of the future teacher of mathematics provides a logical structure of the educational material presentation, which can include the following blocks: a) information (for what purpose information is provided about one or another way of cognitive activity, and how acquired

skills can be used in future professional activities) ; b) value-orientation block, which serves as the basis for the emergence of motives for cooperation and social motivation for engagement in educational and cognitive activities; c) a productive-procedural unit, which presents the effectiveness of the result of educational and cognitive activity, depending on the possession of logical actions and operations.

The formation in a future mathematics teacher the components of self-educational competence of the motivational component does not testify the occurrence of self-educational actions, but the typical feature, the quality of the individual. The motivational component of self-education competence combines those components of the personality that characterize the teacher as a person with his individual perception of the world, his attitude to self-educational activity and is an important condition for the professional growth, the formation and the development of the future teacher.

The second pedagogical condition for the formation of self-educational competence is the pedagogical stimulation of the future teacher of mathematics. In substantiating this condition, we relied on the fact that "stimulation". There is an influence not directly on the person, but on external circumstances with the help of incentives, which, on their part, prompt the person to a certain behavior. In the process of developing the terms, we relied on the following types of pedagogical incentives for vocational and creative training of the future teacher.

The most typical advanced trends in the study of the problem of pedagogical stimulation as a condition for the formation of self-educational competence of the future teacher of mathematics are: extending the study of methodological concepts of pedagogical stimulation of mathematics teacher; intense attention to the methodological direction of research, that can provide the promotion of the idea of pedagogical stimulation in university practice for the preparation of the future teacher of mathematics; scientific and psychological substantiation and disclosure of the mechanism of action of pedagogical stimuli, conditions of the effectiveness of their application in the university pedagogical process.

The third pedagogical condition for the formation of self-educational competence of the future teacher of mathematics is the involvement of students in the research activities. Under the research activity of the future teacher of mathematics, we understand the specially organized process of obtaining and using knowledge, forming a scientific outlook and creative thinking that helps to improve teaching the subject and implementation a creative approach to the school process organization.

The organization of students' research work in the higher educational establishment should be carried out in two directions. The first is that the students' scientific work is within the educational process, which is necessary. This includes the writing the term paper and qualification papers (bachelors', diploma, masters' papers) and participation in special seminars and laboratory classes. The second direction is the students' scientific work outside the educational process. This includes the participation in the work of experimental laboratories, scientific study group, etc. Scientific-research activity is one of the most important forms of the educational process, which promotes the development of creative thinking, responsibility and ability to defend their views. It is an important component of the training the future mathematics teachers during high school education and should be characterized by close systemic interdisciplinary relationships, foresee the students' armament of research methodology, promote not only deepening and expanding knowledge, but also enriching the outlook of students' youth, stimulate the development of independence, creativity potential, intellectual abilities of each person.

For the research work it is necessary to get the student interested in work, help him to choose the problem, he will work on throughout the study and will receive the final result. When planning topics, their lecturers direct them to the maximum scientific research.

The complex of pedagogical conditions that we have defined allows us to effectively build the process of forming the self-educational competence of the future teacher of mathematics in the process of professional training.

ASSESSMENT AS A KEY COMPONENT OF DEVELOPING SKILLS

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In modern conditions of increased competition in labour market on a world scale the problem of the quality of education is a burning issue as contemporary employers make high demands of professional competences. Therefore, educational establishments should be in line with up-to-date requirements defined by labour market, which, in its turn, aims at not only perfect knowledge in the professional sphere, but also developed skills applicable in further work. This fact influences greatly on the assessment process as for many years it was oriented to control of knowledge, while skills were considered to be developed in the course of practice at work. In other words, traditional forms of assessment, which are still in use in many countries, need to be revised and reconsidered.

Making a start from understanding of two generic types of assessment, which are formative and summative, it can be stated that summative assessment is always used in educational process as it is the only proper scoring benchmark of the standard of grades which allows the teachers as well as administration to decide whether the student is permitted to continue education or get a diploma. This fact emphasizes the responsibility of the task makers who should validate their assignments through the procedures of corroboration. Such procedures consist of several stages: 1) pre-exam, including a) content compliance (the task should refer only to the information of the course), b) assignment format (test, essay, short-answer questions, project work, etc.), c) time efficiency (how much time each task takes); 2) while-exam, consisting of a) exam-environment (how many students are there in the classroom, how comfortable/stuffy/warm/cold/noisy/quiet in the classroom, etc.), b) students' level of training (which can be monitored through different types of formative assessment); 3) post-exam, comprising a number of psychometric techniques aimed at analysis of test results (indexes for measuring the amount of internal consistency for an exam, like Cronbach's alpha or Spearman-Brown prophecy formula).

However, summative assessment does not always satisfy the need for controlling the developed skills, which are more successfully monitored through formative assessment that is more linked to learning experience, understanding, and mastering the skills. Formative assessment is mostly oriented to the teacher's feedback, not the score. Consequently, the instructor should retain two key moments of efficient monitoring the development of skills in progress: 1) the assignment should be goaled at the development of certain skills, which should be mentioned in objectives as well as clearly explained to the students (for example, portfolio, concept map, presentation, etc.); 2) feedback should be directed to the clarification of the weak points in work and recommendations for further improvement.

In other words, the assessment is a key factor of educational process that can not only control/monitor students' knowledge and skills, but also improve learning outcomes by correct implementation and following the main principles of assessment application.

UNIVERSITY COURSE TEXTBOOKS WITH A PERSON-ORIENTED APPROACH

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The information society forces educators to create new learning technologies. In the new educational paradigm, student becomes intrinsically central figure in the educational process. From now on, pedagogy should focus on managing information for the implementation of cognitive activities of students, and not on teaching, characteristic for the industrial society era. For this reason, coursebooks should become fundamentally different.

In our study, we are examining primarily a traditional paper-based textbook that remains the most popular amongst other source materials.

The educational information in such coursebook is structured and presented in the form of information study blocks (ISB). Each of the created information study blocks is a system consisting of four subsystem blocks: the basic study block (BSB), the complementary study block (CSB), the signal study block (SSB) and the applied study block (ASB). Worth noticing, that the CSB, the SSB and the ASB must be inserted in the BSB on the principle of "four in one".

The basic study block is formed from separate statements of the written text, which are sequentially numbered and placed in the text according to the logical order of their teaching, providing "the transition from one knowledge to another". The complementary study block consists of didactic materials concerning worldview and popular science, which expand, complement, popularize, and affect the emotional and sensory sphere of the student, thus disrupting the mechanism of information perception. Signal study block consists of performative statements (rules and regulations) that contain especially important and worth paying special attention to or remembering information. The applied study block provides an example of solving a specific real-life problem or task concerning safety topics. It is separated from the main text by the subheading "Example", "Practice", etc.

Consequently, the information study block (ILB) has the form of multilevel, branched hypertext, structural units of which are linked by a single thematic plan, which is increasing the effectiveness of learning through a person-oriented approach.

Working with such textbook on a paper carrier, student is placed in the center of a constructed cognitive environment, and "takes over" information flows from four educational units (blocks) – BSB, CSS, SSB, ASB which are coherent, interferentially enhanced in space and time due to the agreement between the authors about their content, coherence and proper location in the textbook.

Finally, it is noteworthy that such a multi-level structure of information (in contrast to plane, linear) to some extent brings the paper textbook closer to electronic. Moreover, the educational components of such textbook can be transformed into an electronic textbook. And the educational components of such textbook, as separate "clips", are combined by the performative text of the basic study block (BSB) into one coherent whole. Fragmentary, "clip" perception of information, peculiar to modern youth, does not dissipate in such a textbook, but on the contrary, synergistically intensifies each fragment and works on the result: the knowledge acquisition.

VOLUNTARY AND FORCED MIGRATION: TOLERANCE AND LENIENCY

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During global process this topic becomes more and more popular and at the same time becomes important, too. In the 21st century modern world met not only the long-term antiquity challenge, but also new epoch makes new challenges such as migration, which became one of the main problem for the modern developed world. Voluntary or just forced migrations influenced the policy, the economy... Voluntary migration is increasing day by day in developing countries, which facilitates the development of technology, reduces travel, availability of information, diversity of labor market, different pay and other factors.

In modern global countries every person has the right to make decision, choose her/his dwelling place, but on the other hand when we speak about voluntary migration, we must mark that there is forced migration, too. Even today there are many reasons why millions of people have to leave their houses and last their lives in the other countries. There are many reasons, facts and forms of forced migration. And of course there are difference between results, too. In the modern world the number of migrants has increased and this becomes global problem, which has created difficulties not only in demographic terms but in social, economic and political aspects. The main part of migrants don't return to their homeland and reason is political crisis, changeable climate, conflicts and so on and now they live as a migrants. It is interesting see how international organizations are struggling with problems, but before this it is necessary to understand what is difference between "international governance" and "global governance". During international governance, most of government institutions are regulating various issue of state policy, while global governance"- non-governmental, international and transnational institutes, which means that they are more involved in international law than are involved in the process of non-state actors. However, global governance should not be confused with the global government.

According to the global process, countries are more closer to each other, state border is losing its meaning and it isn't difficult to move from one country to another. So people has opportunity to work and make their educational progress. The scourge and education market became global, which allowed people to make a choice based on the international market. This can be a positive aspect, but the problem is that employers have to compete in order to invite the best staff, migratory processes in developing countries and developing countries in developing countries. One of the main factors of voluntary migration is the remuneration that is different in different countries.

Despite the fact that the migration has negative side, it also can benefit the country's economy, which is in remittances, which is the main source of foreign currency inflows in the country and contributes to strengthening local currency.

KIROVOGRAD REGIONAL HISTORY OF JEWISH SUFFERING IN THE DISCOURSE OF MODERN UKRAINIAN EUROPEANISM

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As the “God-chosen” people, the Jews have throughout history been a rather persecuted nation. The reasons for and the details of it have been explored widely and are well known.

The Jewry of the former Russian empire (and later - the Soviet Union) concentrated mostly on territories of modern Ukraine (the present Kirovograd region being one of them) and Byelorussia, partly Moldavia and Lithuania. Law on “the pale of settlement” (annulled on April 2, 1917) prohibited the Jews from living in villages and major cities.

1. Bolsheviks’ attitude towards Jews.
2. The carnage of WWI and its effects on economics of Russian empire and the mentality of its peoples; Soviet repression campaigns of post-October years.
3. Jews in the ranks of the Party; percentage of Jews in the Government and the Cheka (Bolshevik secret police). Line on integrating Jews into society, a chance to enforce and pursue the objective of their nation: unification within the limits of the “promised land”. Creation of the autonomous Republic of Birobijan.
4. Jewish quasi-national political bodies (the Jewish Comsomol, Young Communists’ League), national cultural, sports and trade union societies (“Maccabee”, “Histadrut” etc.). The Soviet State with its dominant Marx’s doctrine on proletariat having no nationality.

(All points to be illustrated with examples from cancelled criminal cases, now preserved at the State Archives of Kirovograd Region:

A 20-year Jewish orphan girl Hawa Aptekar, a house-help (parents killed in a pogrom) sentenced to three years of exile to the Urals for taking part in the Jewish scout movement and applying for a visa to Palestine in 1927;

Riva Zlobinskaya, b. 1902, twice arrested for allegedly being a member of a “Jewish nationalist counterrevolutionary underground organization”, tried and exiled in 1926 and 1931, tried again on the same charges and executed in 1938. Further examples will be optionally provided and cited).

5. Criminal cases against individual Jews, their national organizations as a pretext for their disbandment; further strengthening of central power in the USSR.

6. After the Molotov-Ribbentrop Pact many Polish Jews fled to the Soviet Union, considering it “state of equal possibilities”, “workers’ paradise” etc. They were later tried for illegal border crossing, anti-Soviet propaganda and for “being members of anti-Soviet underground organizations”.

(Point illustrated by cases on Simon and Aron Igelnik, Franz Lynchevsky and many others.)

7. As Kirovograd region is the birthplace of Leo Trotsky, there were many criminal cases against his followers (A. Kupersmidt, V. Yablonskaya, Z. Daenman and others).

8. Jews as one of the marginalized groups to take the brunt of Nazi terror in the occupied territories of the SU. The legacy of war: several detention camps, ghettos, killing places in Kirovograd region (now marked with monuments). The Holocaust history here has been thoroughly researched and made public (examples, photos and names provided).

9. Strict economic and political measures by German occupying forces, policies of national segregation adding to the atmosphere of fear and mutual distrust among the locals.

10. “The righteous of the peoples of the world” (examples in Kirovograd region).

11. Consequential “roadmap” of Ukrainian Europeanism nowadays.

THE MAN AS A SUBJECT, THE WOMAN AS A SUBJECT

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The author in her theses of the Author considers key questions of methodologists.

A man, being alive and capable (with his common sense of a man), - exists as a man – human being, or as a Subject external ("natural ("physical") and natural-social"), in his external, or material, world of a man, being a man – human being as such, and he exists as a man-individual, or as a Subject internal ("artificial ("cultural", "ideological")"), in his inner, or ideal, world of a man, being himself a man -individual as such. A woman, being alive and capable (with her common sense of a woman), - exists as a woman – human being, or as a Subject external ("natural ("physical") and natural-social"), in her external, or material, world of a woman, being a woman – human being as such, and she exists as a woman-individual, or as a Subject internal ("artificial ("cultural", "ideological")"), in her inner, or ideal, world of a woman, being herself a woman-individual as such.

Post-Platonists, naturalists and cultural anthropologists who positioned themselves and keep positioning themselves as rationalists have created and are creating for themselves, researchers, and for the readers, analyzing their personal matrices of post-Platonists, their theories of researchers about an internal Man ("cultural ("ideological"), or rational"), as a reasonable intelligent person ("homo sapiens Sapiens") with her personal rational mind of the homo sapiens Sapiens in her inner space of the homo sapiens Sapiens. The post-Platonists have previously conceptualized the man and the woman as "Homo Adamus", and today they describe both the man as a human being, the spiritual person ("Homo Spiritus"), and the woman – either as the inner person or as the spiritual person ("Homo Spiritus"), ignoring the natural strategy of the man and the natural strategy of the woman.

Post-Aristotelians, naturalists and social anthropologists, positioning themselves as critics, researched in their personal mental matrices of the scientists the mental matrices of other people, and the ideas of the speakers, representatives of various ethnic groups of people (outside of their political statuses of people), and the principles of the speakers in their political statuses of the speakers - the values of citizens and the values of subjects as representatives of different nations of people. The Post-Aristotelians philosophized and keep philosophizing with one another about an external Man ("social", "objective"), or about a critical Man, as an intelligent Man in his outer space of an intelligent Man in his personal critical mind of an intelligent Man, conceptualizing the man as an Anthropos ("Homo Sapiens") and as a rational being ("Homo sapiens") and a woman as an Anthropos ("Homo Sapiens") and as a rational being ("Homo sapiens"), without realizing either who is the man naturally (strategically) and naturally (tactically (socially and culturally)) as such, nor who is the woman naturally (strategically) and naturally (tactically (ideologically)) as such claiming that they, the post-Aristotelians, studied the nature of the external man as a social being and the nature of the external women as a social being.

Who is the man as a Subject socio-cultural or ideological as such?! He is the man alive in the presence of living and able (with his personal common sense of the man) as such. Who is the woman as a Subject socio-cultural or ideological as such?! She is the woman alive in the presence of living and able (with her personal common sense of the woman) as such.

PRIORITY DIRECTIONS OF DEVELOPMENT OF INDUSTRIAL PRODUCTION ENTERPRISES OF INNOVATIVE TYPE

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Restructuring and identifying key factors to ensure effectiveness in eliminating negative impacts on the country's economy will protect against destructive external influences. This will increase energy efficiency and will form an effective system of innovation and investment climate in the state. The inconsistency of the existing system of public administration with the innovation transformation of production-economic relations is due to the need to increase the efficiency of the implementation of innovative projects at enterprises. Reductions in the number of licensing documents in the area of economic activity and their types subject to licensing, the abolition of regulatory acts, which complicate the conduct of entrepreneurial activity and reduce the number of state supervision bodies, will have a positive effect.

In order to support investment activity and protect the rights of investors, it is necessary to create a favorable field of protection of private property rights, including judicial authorities, to harmonize with the legislation of the European Union the provisions of the country's legislation on the protection of the rights of national and foreign investors and creditors, the protection of economic competition, the introduction of effective incentive mechanisms investment activity, based on the best world practice.

It is advisable to highlight the main causes of the current destructive changes in the field of the formation and implementation of the innovation and investment concept of enterprise restructuring, consisting in the inability of modern management tools to maintain competitive positions due to lower volumes of production and low innovation activity, high customs duties on imported raw materials, low level of market infrastructure, almost complete lack of investment resources for the production of technological modern tion production. Therefore, in view of the above justification, the need for the formation, growth, rational use of the potential of the restructuring of production and economic systems and the key factor in ensuring their balanced functioning, which is likely to be realized through the attraction of investment capital to the processes of the reproductive management system modernization, updating, reforming, engineering, cross-engineering and reengineering of the production-economic, technical-technological and external ekonomichnoyi activity.

Activation of innovation development through restructuring changes can only be achieved through the use of appropriate composition of methods, practical tools, set of actions and procedures of organizational, managerial, technological, legal and regulatory nature. The whole targeted socio-economic acceleration is presented, which will allow to intensify the process of introducing innovations and intensify the whole-oriented structural and dynamic changes in order to ensure the general economic acceleration in the state.

ОРГАНІЗАЦІЯ ТА УПРАВЛІННЯ ОХОРОНОЮ ЗДОРОВ'Я У ПОЛЬЩІ

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Польща має багато спільних рис в соціально-економічних та територіальних аспектах з Україною, що зумовлює актуальність дослідження її системи охорони здоров'я.

Відповідно до статті 68 Конституції Республіки Польща 1997 р., всі громадяни, незалежно від їхнього фінансового становища, мають повне право на рівний доступ до медичних послуг, що фінансуються з державних коштів, а також відповідно до статті 49 встановлено право кожного громадянина на охорону здоров'я, медичну допомогу та медичне страхування.

Центральним органом, який здійснює управління сектором охорони здоров'я в країні та його організацію, є Міністерство охорони здоров'я, яке відповідає за національну політику, її реалізацію, координацію, розробку керівних принципів та рішень з проблем здоров'я, оцінює рівень медичної допомоги.

Територіальні органи охорони здоров'я на кожному рівні (гміна, пакистан, воєводство) несуть відповідальність за стан здоров'я населення, планування надання медичних послуг та швидкої медичної допомоги.

Державна адміністрація на рівні воєводств забезпечує ведення реєстру закладів охорони здоров'я, прийняття рішення про внесення або вилучення до нього громадських та недержавних закладів, утворення таких закладів, контроль за ними на території воєводства.

Воєводське самоврядування, та на рівні повіту і гміни забезпечують реалізацію завдань, віднесених до їх повноважень законами, виконують функції засновника щодо створення громадських закладів охорони здоров'я, забезпечують надання медичних послуг іншими закладами у разі ліквідації громадського закладу охорони здоров'я.

Особливостями системи охорони здоров'я у Польщі є широкі повноваження органів самоврядування на рівні воєводств, що реалізуються шляхом безпосереднього управління та фінансування медичних закладів та здійснення контролю за їх діяльністю.

EPIC EXPERIENCE AND FOLKLOR INTEGRATION (Based on the novel "The Dead Earth" by I. Shikhli)

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This article examines the different forms of folk traditions in the epic work, including the novel of I.Shikhli "My dead world". The main attention devoted to such folk traditions that play a significant role in the form the archetype in creation of original images.

Keywords: epos, epic culture, customs and customs, culture, literature, folklore, prose, archetype.

The Azerbaijani literature of the twentieth century has gone through a complex and controversial stage of development, such as society itself and the people itself. The people have preferred to reflect the peculiarities of the people throughout their existence, as well as preserving their existence, language, religion, culture, art, traditions, ethnocultural thought and lifestyle, as well as

their literary literature. As you know, fiction is primarily a product of folk thought and morality. "Today contemporary critical thinking puts a completely right concept into literary circulation," literature is so great that it stands on strong ethno-cultural basis. Epos can not be a genius that can not be based on epic culture "(N.Jafarov). In this sense, in contemporary novel, the Azerbaijani novelist appears to have its own epic and epic culture "(1,47).

Ismail Shikhli is one of the epos, epic culture-based artists of the 20th century Azerbaijani prose, and one of the novels is the "Dead World". It is known that Ismayil Shikhli wrote his name to the history of Azerbaijani literature as the author of the novel "Crazy Kur" for ever. Even though the novel was published, it has also been valued as one of the greatest achievements of the epic type of the epic in the last century. A new breath of literary-cultural life was an example of a different perspective that most of us expected in the past but could not be witnesses.

The people begin to lose their strength and power at that time, or begin to lose weight, starting from the roots of the original experiments, in the words of Ch.Aitmatov, "manqurt". The novel of the novel "Crazy Kur" by I. Shikhly is an artistic work, and in this respect it has become an alarm signal. The protagonist of the novel says, "Although the world of Jahandar's auntie is a dead, dying, dead world, it is not a past world for the writer, it is an example of immortal, eternal, eternal national qualities, worth living" (2,47).

The image of Jahandar Agha introduced us to our national identity. Professor Nizami Jafarov spoke about an interesting issue while speaking to Ismail Shikhli. He writes: "For my sincerest belief, Ilya Shikhli's creative work before Crazy Kura does not lead to Crazy Kura ... From the" Front lines "to the" Diverted Roads ", almost none of his works" Crazy Kura "(3,169). It is possible to add one aspect to the agreement of the prominent scientist. Indeed, no work of the writer shows his writing of "Crazy Kür", but "Crazy Kur" had a serious impact on the artist's subsequent creative search, in fact, somehow became the basis of the next stage. "Crazy Kur" created the novel "My dead world".

The main common feature of the novels is that folklore elements, folk thought, national traditions are very strongly expressed in these works. Apparently, my "dead world" may seem to be some logical continuation of the novel "Crazy Kur". In fact, the novel is a complete original work. "At first glance it is possible to assume that the position of Jahangar master is played by heroic pafos rather than tragic pope. Not only because Jahang Agha is a physically strong person like a fairy tale, the heroes of the epic, his head almost sank into the ceiling, his arms are almost slippery, his horsepower is skillful, he is capable of playing the rifle, shooting in an eye, shining in the air with bullets breaks the dagger, breaks it down, defeats the enemy without knowing it. And most importantly, because of the fact that Jahandar agha combines his / her qualities, such as physical strength, fearlessness, brave, bravery, with a public-national position (with hereditary properties protecting herd habits) knows what to do and does not face the long-lasting hesitation of questions such as "What to do?" and "How to do it?" (4,17).

One of the main issues that arouse interest in this fact is Jahandar Agha is a reminder of the tale and heroes of the epic. Interestingly, the "Crazy Kur" also reminds more of Jahandar Aga's tales, heroes of the epic, while most of the stories in the novel, "My Deadly Life," even women's characters, are the tale and heroes of the epic. No mention in this book, which we have written in Ismayil Shikhli's novel "Crazy Kur," does not happen accidentally, does not go with stixy.

Based on this memoir, the archetype, which is often used in modern literary criticisms (together with philosophy and psychology), stands out. K.Yunq, the founder of analytic psychology, was the first scientist who made his first appearance in science. "In the later years of literature, the term" Arxetip "is used to describe more general, fundamental and universal mythological motifs, the scheme of the initial imaginations based on all kinds of art, including the mythological structure ..." (5,111). Arkethep speaks in a wider sense as an embodiment of the "collective experience of the people" (A.Y.Bolchakova).

There is a need to focus on this issue before it is fully understood. Archetype, the embodiment of collective experience or collective memory, is the repeated repetition of the original image, motif, behavioral norm, model, and subsequent repetition. These, including the image, may be different. With respect to the image of Ismail Shikhli's novel "My dead world", it is possible to say that this image is closely related to the hero, the warrior image and the basis of his code in the collective memory of the people.

In fact, in the novel the author did not create a series of warriors, and that was not the purpose. The artist portrayed the images of ordinary human beings, who still have their deformed lifestyle. The novel has a conventional venue and has attempted to imagine the lives of several generations in this

unchanging space. It is not difficult to notice that only in the Soviet era, people who are imprisoned violate the basic principles of the Code of Conduct are emerging in this area.

The characters in the novel do not name the oguz bey in "Dede Gorgud", the names of the deceased in "Koroglu", and they do not emphasize their return. They simply live in the arsenal of warriors and warriors who come from collective memory. The characteristic features of these images include courage, loyalty, greatness, greatness, courage, the past and all its essential aspects, to host hostility as men, to preserve traditions and so on. such as identity.

Shamsaddin Agha met with his mother to consult with his brother Hasan Agha, who accidentally and accidentally killed Aladdin. "Shamidin heard the fragrance of the cacao as he entered the tree. He held a little foot on the door, and then stepped into his mother's footsteps. In the light of the seventies, the anguish of his mother, whose face was apparent in the light of the light, knelt in his arms and kissed his hand, without thinking about the mixed question; and the wife is from her son's forehead. Shamiddin Agha was so much in front of the parent, and only when he pointed out, he sat on the bridge. It was the custom of the woman: no one, who did not call himself, dared and could not enter his room unauthorized; to sit with him in that inn "(6, 248).

Rose (including Omar Koha) is not simply a lumberbug of a house, but also an example of regulating the existing norms of the bay. It is also a distinctive image of mythology, an elderly folklore, and an unwittingly unwanted function of the trunk. He stands in the notion of the society in which he is depicted, and that he inherited this status, not by age, but primarily for his lifetime. In fact, the ghulus, Omar Koha, are objects that prevent the transformation of cosmos into chaos in the form of space.

This function, which they perform by unofficial status, is executed by Kassefli with its official status. Those who are compelled to meet him usually ask: "But you, my uncle, are you talking to me as a" Gepo ", or like a Kabe's uncle? How can I answer you? "(6,265). He holds the status he has acquired before the official status at all stages of his life. Those who communicate with her want to follow the rules of the traditional national society, not the state they can not accept.

Space does not change in space, people change. Frightened by the cloak of the society in which they first lived, they start to play horse at the place where the transposition is normed, and they try to apply new behavioral norms in line with their own morals. Mrs. Gullu says: "How often, do you have sex with your wife and child? - Keep your mouth clean, moon snow. - She is old and she is old. I have my name. - I know. But more of your passion has gone "(6,345). In another episode, Omar Koha acts as a ghully lady. It protects its name. For Fatullayev, the name does not mean anything extraordinary. Ms. Gullu and Omar Koha have justified themselves and lived up to their normal lives. The fate of those who do not know the name of Hondu ends with the dog.

As the people replace the embryos, the morality of society also begins to change gradually. But the writer used an interesting priyom. The number of people who are still trying to change the morality of the present society has diminished, and the writer has shown that the fate of almost all of them has gone unrecognizably. The dog breaks the dog. "The man's hand was getting closer to the bucket. With a trumpet, the roar of a horse became one. The balls were scattered around the globe. Fatullayev was on the table. The crucifix looked at his face as he had been in the black blood, and dropped from the door into a horse blade and slipped into the horse's back "(6,362).

One of the exciting episodes of Romance is the return of the Hellenic father to his homeland after many years of separation. The composer, who was in the country before his father, saw the grapes being planted in the countryside of the Alkazakh and Chirag children. The houses were extinguished, and only one stone house was left, and they had a poultry farm. The incubator chickens were rising around it "(6,364). They dumped the dwelling with the Personality Code, but they could not destroy the inhabitants of the country. The band came to live in the dorm, and the dog was still living in Alan. Hasan Agha can not meet with his son. He knows that the descendants of Ala are left, that his son is here and that he can easily find his life. Hassan Agha, who suffered from anxiety in the country, is dying from home.

"My dead world" is one of the interesting, but not less successful, of the writer's work. The hard truths that „Crazy Kur “ could not say in his own time, the writer was able to express himself with high craftsmanship in this roma. It is also important to note that one of the main artistic tools cited by the artist was an archetype of collective memory. The power of the novel also rests on ethnic and cultural grounds, epos, epic culture.

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